

Annual Report
1999-2000

The Rewards of Rice Research

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The Rewards of Rice Research

Why should anyone give money to rice research? What would the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) achieve with it? What should an "investor" hope to accomplish by donating it?

These are perhaps three of the most important questions facing IRRI and its partners in 2000—the year of the Institute's 40th anniversary and the start of a new millennium.

In 1999, IRRI and the other 15 centers that make up the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR) were all urged to rename their donors, investors. This was done because most donors are increasingly seen as wanting some kind of "return" on the money they are giving to agricultural research.

IRRI welcomed this move. This report is part of our ongoing efforts to make sure the rewards of rice research are obvious to everyone—not just those who have supported our work for so long, but also those who we hope will support it in the future.

The easy answer to the question, What are the returns on rice research?, is that it helps to ensure food security and alleviate hunger and poverty. This is the basic reason that so many nations, organizations, and groups have given so generously to IRRI over the past 40 years.

But in an era of stiff competition for development assistance, that is clearly no longer enough. Although we still face the same problems of hunger and poverty, we cannot expect people, organizations, or governments to continue to give without showing them more clearly what we have achieved in the past and can achieve in the future.

The theme of this report, the rewards of rice research, is just the first step by IRRI to deal with this most important of challenges. We are determined to show the world, and our investors, that it is essential they continue to invest in rice research if they are sincerely committed to eradicating hunger and poverty in Asia.

At IRRI, we have adapted an old saying to read "Give people a bowl of rice and you feed them for a day; help them grow better rice and you feed them, and their families, for a lifetime."

This is the real reward of rice research: a safe and secure future for all those who eat it.

A handwritten signature in cursive script that reads "Ronald P. Cantrell".

Ronald P. Cantrell
Director General

The Rewards Are There for All to See

No comprehensive study has ever been made of the actual economic rewards of rice research, or what IRRI has achieved over its 40-year history in terms of economic development.

However, rice research conducted by the national agricultural research systems of rice-producing nations, and supported by IRRI, has made important progress in many areas. These achievements involve genetically improved seeds, innovative cultivation practices, and better management practices for sustaining soil, water, and biotic resources.

Perhaps most significantly, the first modern rice variety, IR8, released in 1966, shifted the yield potential from 4 to 10 tons per hectare, allowing farmers to significantly increase production despite limited land resources.

Over the years, rice scientists have also been able to incorporate ever-improving elements of resistance to major insects and diseases in successive modern varieties. This has not only helped to reduce farmers' dependence on harmful agrochemicals but also decreased costs and thus boosted incomes. Scientists have also bred varieties that mature faster and so save land area; that have improved grain quality and so allow farmers to obtain better prices; and that tolerate drought, submergence, and poor soils and so allow farmers to maintain yields even under difficult conditions.

These and other technological advances have undoubtedly changed the face of rice cultivation in humid and subhumid Asia over the past 40 years. Rice production in Asia grew from 240 million tons in 1966 to about 530 million tons in 1999, much faster than the regional population, which has almost doubled over the past 35 years.

In Bangladesh, Asia's most land-scarce and impoverished country, rice production increased from 14 million tons in 1966 to 31 million tons in 1999. Almost all of this gain came from yield increases, as farmers shifted from traditional to modern rice.

Rigorous studies estimating the rate of return on investments in rice research are hard to come by. Yale University economist Robert Evenson has summarized evidence on the rate of return estimated from the determinants of total factor productivity for 10 Asian countries and concluded that the marginal internal rate of return was 59 percent. This indicates how substantial the rewards of rice research may be in economic terms. Although more work needs to be done, the technological progress in rice cultivation has undoubtedly brought huge benefits to an estimated 250 million rice farmers and nearly 2.6 billion rice consumers.

As the unit cost of rice production has declined with higher yields, farmers have been able to offer rice to consumers at affordable prices, without their profits diminishing.

Unit costs have declined by up to 30 percent and the price of rice adjusted for inflation has declined by nearly 40 percent since 1960. Because the poor spend more than 50 percent of their income on rice, this decline in real prices has helped alleviate poverty in many Asian nations. It has also helped save scarce foreign exchange that governments would have otherwise spent on importing food to keep prices affordable to the poor in times of reduced domestic production.

Poverty is still far too common in many parts of Asia, but it would be even more widespread and desperate without the progress achieved so far through rice research.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Mahabub Hossain'.

Dr. Mahabub Hossain
Head, Social Sciences Division

A Few Case Histories

Proving the human and economic benefits of rice research is not a difficult task. In fact, there's not one rice-growing country on Earth that hasn't benefited in some fashion from international agricultural research. But quantifying those benefits in dollar terms can be more difficult. As the following case histories illustrate, any attempt to put figures on the benefits of rice research requires a precise answer to the question, What would the cost have been, both locally and internationally, if researchers had not intervened?

Bangladesh

Disastrous flooding has long been a harsh aspect of life in Bangladesh.

Every wet season, the three great rivers, the Ganges, the Brahmaputra, and the Meghna, swollen with snowmelt or heavy rainfall from the Himalayas, collide with high tides or, worse still, with cyclones, as they rush south toward the Indian Ocean. They spill out to inundate nearly 40 percent of the country every year and can cover up to 70 percent during years of disastrous floods. The water can also cover the land for months.

Growing deepwater rice was once the only way thousands of small Bangladeshi farmers could use the floodwater for their annual crops. Yields were low, about 2 tons per hectare, and, in the 1970s, as many as 70 percent of the people lived below the poverty line.

In 1974, the flood was far worse than normal. It destroyed about 2.5 million hectares of deepwater rice and the land remained inundated for too long to replant and try again. Agricultural laborers lost jobs, wage rates declined, and, with the next crop a year away, rice prices trebled. Thirty thousand people died in the resulting famine. Thousands more were saved by international food aid.

A revolution soon began in Bangladesh's rice fields. IRRI stepped in to support the fledgling Bangladesh Rice Research Institute. More than a hundred of the country's rice scientists underwent IRRI training for their M.S. and Ph.D. degrees. Then, armed with new technology and using abundant underground water, the farmers began switching to irrigated dry-season rice crops. They began growing modern high-yielding varieties developed by IRRI, or plants bred locally from IRRI parents. Yields rose to as much as 6 tons per hectare.

Gradually, the area planted to vulnerable wet-season crops dwindled from 4.8 to 1.6 million hectares, and safe dry-season crops rose from 0.5 to 3.3 million hectares.

In 1998, another flood occurred, even worse than those before, and there were predictions of famine, epidemics of sickness, widespread unemployment, spiraling food prices, and as many as two million deaths.

None of these things happened. The worst flood in a decade destroyed 2 million tons of rice, but there was no famine. The deepwater rice crop had become unimportant and its loss was quickly compensated for by the dry-season harvest. As the water receded, Bangladeshi farmers planted new dry-season crops and their subsequent harvest was the best in the country's history.

Bangladesh was spared the cost of importing food; the international community was spared the expense of emergency food aid.

An economic analysis of the Bangladesh case concluded that, for a total investment of US\$18 million per year in rice research, irrigation development, and agricultural extension, the country's total cost savings amounted to \$229 million per year over 20 years. Had this savings been invested to yield a 10 percent annual return, the total benefit to Bangladesh would have been a staggering \$33.5 billion.

The Toul Koktrap Research Station in Suay Rieng: destroyed by years of war, it has now reopened.

In 1999, Cambodian rice farmers produced a record 3.8 million tons of unmilled rice, 220,000 tons more than their country needed. It was the fourth successive year of surplus production, following the harvest of 1995, when, for the first time in 25 years, Cambodia grew enough rice to feed its people. Since then, the country has been a rice exporter.

Just 20 years earlier, the country lay in ruins after years of war and internal conflict. The population had been decimated and the production of rice, the staple food, had all but ceased. Seed stocks for the country's traditional rice varieties had been eaten by people on the edge of starvation. Cambodia had been forced in 1980 to import 300,000 tons of rice to feed its surviving six million people.

IRRI joined the effort to rebuild Cambodia late in 1988, when it helped form the Cambodia-IRRI-Australia Project (CIAP). With funding from the Australian Agency for International Development, and in conjunction with the local Ministry of Agriculture, Forests, and Fisheries, CIAP launched research programs to study varietal improvement, integrated nutrient management, agricultural engineering, integrated pest management, and farming and social systems.

At the same time, it began a huge training effort. After the warfare and genocide, Cambodia had no researchers, extension workers, or technicians left. With help from IRRI's Training Center, more than 1,300 scientists and technical support workers have been trained to staff the country's agricultural research system.

On the farms, one of the first steps was the introduction of short-duration, high-yielding rice varieties. Double-cropping began under rainfed conditions, reducing the incidence of crop failure because of drought or floods.

Seeds for traditional varieties, which, in Cambodia, had been eaten by hungry people, were found in safe storage at IRRI's International Rice Genebank in the Philippines. At the request of the Cambodian government, the seeds of 765 varieties were returned to be grown again in their native fields.

CIAP researchers developed a simple soil classification system, and taught farmers how to use fertilizers correctly. They brought in leveling technology to take the dry heights and saturated hollows out of farmers' fields. Integrated pest management techniques, adapted by CIAP for local conditions, increased the profitability of farms through the introduction of more sustainable, lower-polluting pest control methods.

Cambodia's rice industry is now not only back on its feet, it is running strongly. Rice yields from the country's rainfed areas have increased from 1.35 to 1.75 tons per hectare.

At the end of 2001, CIAP will be phased out and local rice research systems will take over. IRRI's part in the recovery will have cost about US\$18.6 million over 13 years. Direct benefits to Cambodia are counted in the hundreds of millions of dollars.

Eastern India

IRRI scientists are sharing the credit for a minor revolution that has swept the poor rice-growing communities of eastern India.

Ten years ago, the farmers of Assam, Bihar, Orissa, West Bengal, and the eastern parts of Uttar Pradesh and Madhya Pradesh had been all but overlooked by advances in rice science.

So IRRI proposed a project aimed at improving their lifestyles and lifting their rice output. It was supported by the International Fund for Agricultural Development and joined by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, state agricultural universities, groups of farmers, and nongovernment organizations.

From the outset, it was pioneering research.

On the one hand, local scientists had never before conducted on-farm research, and, on the other, the farmers had never conceived of a dialogue with scientific researchers. Sorting out how it should be done occupied a big part of the early years. It was a problem exacerbated by the fact that the area had a population of 480 million, with thousands of rice farms, most of them less than one hectare in size, but covering a total of nearly 27 million hectares.

Starting in 1990, research teams visited hundreds of farm families to discuss their management practices. They studied different farming systems, varieties that were being grown, the way water and other resources were used, and how different farmers, including women, managed their crops. Then they devised technologies for improvement. In the process, strong working bonds were formed among scientists, various institutions, and farmers.

Care was taken never to expect additional investment from the farmers. Rather, the researchers sought to modify farm management practices within the farmers' meager resources.

New techniques were passed on through farmer-to-farmer contact, farm visits, demonstrations, and circulation of concise printed material. More than 500 people were trained by IRRI scientists, including local researchers and extension workers. Farmers were encouraged to improve gradually—to first increase their yield, then consolidate for a season or two before setting out to achieve the next increase.

Eventually, at IRRI's initiative, the collected fragments of management advice were assembled into a 250-page manual titled "Rainfed Rice Production: Best Strategies in Eastern India."

Three thousand English-language copies are being printed, and the state authorities are being encouraged to not only adapt the manual for region-specific application but also to translate it and circulate it to farmers.

Over the past four years, all of the increase in India's rice production has come from the six states of eastern India. Farmers' yields have grown by an average of 380 kilograms per hectare, adding a total of about 10.2 million tons of rice to India's national harvest. Yields are expected to keep rising until, within five years, they reach about 3.5 tons per hectare, or nearly three times the level of ten years ago.

The New Plants

For four decades, rice scientists have been running an almost desperate race to keep ahead of the world's growing population. In that time, IRRI's plant breeders have released 318 new rice varieties for the farmers of Asia. Many more have come from scientists in national research systems. So far, the scientists are winning. The world's population has doubled over 40 years, but rice production has risen by about 116 percent, and there are fewer hungry mouths today than there were in 1960.

But the race is far from over.

Hunger and poverty still stain the fabric of humankind. By 2025, Asia will have about four billion people, and, to give each of them enough food, rice production will have to increase by as much as 50 percent.

How will it be achieved?

Asia has no more land on which to expand rice production. Farmers are flocking to the cities in pursuit of an easier life. Water is rapidly becoming a scarce commodity, and concern for the environment rules out any greater use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides as a means of lifting rice production.

IRRI scientists and their national collaborators are working on many methods to make rice farming more productive. But the main hopes for the future still lie within the Institute's tissue culture laboratories and plant breeding greenhouses.

Somehow, the plants themselves must be given the capacity to fill the future food order.

Providing much-needed hope are the limitless possibilities of biotechnology and genetic engineering. Given these new scientific tools, IRRI's researchers have moved beyond the notion of rice providing little more of nutritional value than a steaming bowl of carbohydrates. New varieties promise a revolution in the health and well-being of billions of the world's poor, by delivering daily doses of micronutrients.

The race to feed humanity may not be over, but IRRI is determined to remain in the lead.

Sisters of Nutrition

In a close-packed suburb of the Philippine capital, Manila, a group of 27 young sisters at a Roman Catholic convent has played a vital role in what may prove to be a significant step toward improving nutrition in the developing world.

Their food was prepared and eaten (photo below) under scientific supervision.

“Micronutrient deficiency could be like polio—a thing of the past.”

For six months, their convent became a laboratory. Every mouthful of their food was measured, every activity monitored, every change in body weight noted. And about every month, despite their fear and reluctance, their blood was taken for testing.

It was an extraordinary act of charity, helping to prove that a new experimental variety of rice could, at no cost to anybody, wipe out the misery of iron-deficiency anemia for countless millions of the world’s poor.

The results of the trial have delighted IRRI researchers. Many of the religious sisters, aged between 20 and 30 years, were clinically anemic while on a control diet of ordinary market rice. But, after eating experimental rice IR68144, the serum ferritin levels in their blood leaped, in many cases two or three times higher.

It was the first big human consumption trial for a variety of rice developed at IRRI and found, quite by chance, to be high in both iron and zinc, vital

micronutrients that are normally deficient in a rice-heavy diet.

The experiment sought to discover whether the high levels of iron and zinc in IR68144 could be absorbed by the sisters’ bodies after the rice had been processed, cooked, and digested.

Despite the positive results, a larger human consumption trial will begin soon, in a final effort to convince nutritionists that the new rice is as good as it sounds. This time it will involve nearly 200 religious sisters from six to eight convents in the Manila area. Half of them will be fed the high-iron rice, the other half ordinary market rice, over a nine-month period. The trial will be supervised by scientists from the Philippines and the United States.

IRRI’s search for a new rice variety rich in micronutrients began in 1993, with the knowledge that commercial rice varieties were satisfying hunger but falling short of properly nourishing a vast number of people.

Where rice is the staple diet, about two billion people—nearly one-third of the world’s popula-

tion—suffer from iron-deficiency anemia. About 60 percent of all pregnant women in Asia and 40 percent of schoolchildren are iron-deficient. It impairs immunity and reduces physical and mental capacities. It accounts for up to 20 percent of maternal deaths.

When the search for the new micronutrient-rich rice began, IRRI was simultaneously striving to grow new varieties with the ability to thrive in poor soils and cold temperatures. They were being developed by traditional breeding methods. Quite by chance, it was discovered that one of the varieties designed to tolerate low temperatures had also inherited a richness in iron and zinc from one of its parents. Almost as a bonus, it had good flavor, texture, and cooking qualities. And, to please the farmers, it was also high-yielding.

Its grain was found to contain 21 parts per million of iron, about double the normal iron content of rice, and it also had about 34 parts per million of zinc.

Zinc is known to enhance the body's capacity to absorb iron. It is also essential for a healthy immune system, and it combats both diarrhea and cholesterol accumulation in blood vessels.

The question of whether or not the minerals in IR68144 and

other traditional varieties were available after processing and eating underwent study at Cornell University, in New York, where the rice was eaten by laboratory rats and exposed to cultures of human colon cells. Both experiments were positive for absorption of the micronutrient elements.

Then some high-iron varieties were fed experimentally to a family of two parents and four children living near IRRI's headquarters in the Philippine province of Laguna. All but the father were clinically anemic. After the family members ate varieties Milagrosa and Xua Bue Nuo for two months, their serum ferritin levels rose dramatically, to the point where the lowest of them was double the level recommended for good health.

Despite their excitement, the IRRI researchers accept that they still have a long way to go. They hope the next 200-strong consumption trial will finally convince nutritionists. Then seeds from IR68144 will be given to agricultural research organizations in various countries for adaptability testing and to begin the painstaking process of crossbreeding to give the new plant pest and disease resistance as well as hardiness for local conditions.

The part they didn't like: blood testing.

IR68144, or its offspring, should then be released to farmers in two or three years, and the world's poorer people will begin eating their way to better health.

Meanwhile, IRRI's search for more nutritious rice continues. The project's coordinator, Dr. Glenn Gregorio, says he's confident that a new variety can be bred with an even higher iron content. But, for now, IR68144 is attracting all the attention.

"At a dinner we held, during a workshop on improving human nutrition through agriculture, we ate the high-iron grain," Dr. Gregorio explains. "Scientists, nutritionists, and policymakers were there. The grain quality was equal to that of some of the best varieties, but the aroma was better." ■

Dr. Glenn B. Gregorio began his career in science as a student in a poor rural high school on the island of Mindanao, in the southern Philippines.

He designed a solar drier for agricultural products. It didn't go into commercial production, but it won his way through local, provincial, and national competitions to having him named one of the Philippines' Ten Outstanding Young Scientists in 1981.

Soon afterwards, he left Bukidnon, on Mindanao, where both his parents taught at the local agricultural university, and entered the University of the Philippines Los Baños, the home of IRRI.

He earned his B.S. degree in agriculture, majoring in agronomy. Then he gained his Master's degree in plant

breeding and, later, his Ph.D. in plant genetics.

During his studies, he joined IRRI's plant breeding department as a research aide in 1986. Fourteen years later, he is still breeding new plants at IRRI.

His wife, Myla, is a biochemist. They have three daughters, Micah, age 6; Liwai, 3; and Patricia, just 2 weeks old.

At age 34, Glenn Gregorio is driven by a determination to help the poorest of the poor. He remembers the poor rural folk of his childhood on Mindanao.

"My heart is really with those people," he says, "and I really feel I can help them. If this new variety is successful, then micronutrient deficiency may be a part of history—like smallpox and polio. But that's still just a dream."

Golden Rice

Another IRRI project that offers a dramatic improvement in human nutrition has attracted worldwide attention.

Researchers are developing the so-called "golden" rice, varieties that have been genetically engineered to produce high levels of beta-carotene, the precursor to vitamin A.

The prospect of offering daily doses of vitamin A to millions of poor people in their staple food has excited nutritionists and health authorities alike.

"This is work we've got to do, and we can't do it half-heartedly."

Tiny shards of green struggle from miniscule specks of tissue.

The United Nations says that about two million children under five years of age die every year because of vitamin A deficiency, and as many as 124 million could be sufferers. Vitamin A deficiency impairs their vision, causes blindness, and makes them susceptible to a host of other diseases, such as measles and diarrhea.

The campaign to develop a variety of rice rich in vitamin A began more than 10 years ago. Researchers at the Institute of Plant Sciences at Switzerland's Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich eventually selected three genes, two from a daffodil and one from a bacterium, combined them in the laboratory, then inserted them into rice.

The mature grain glowed with the golden color of beta-carotene, the yellow-orange compound that gives carrots their color. It is the world's most common source of vitamin A.

The freshly engineered germplasm, and the genes, have been passed to IRRI in the hope that scientists at the Institute will be able to transfer the genetic pathway for beta-carotene production into popular, high-yielding indica varieties.

At present, this pathway exists only in a japonica variety named T309, which is widely used in biotechnology experiments because it is very responsive to tissue cultures.

According to IRRI plant biotechnologist, Dr. Swapan

Datta, two different approaches are being made to the task of passing the beta-carotene genes down to commercial varieties. One involves biotechnology, and the other traditional breeding.

He hopes that within two years he will be able to insert the new genes directly into commercial varieties and confirm not only that they have been incorporated but are also functioning through three generations. The traditional breeding program, involving painstaking crossing, growing, and observation, will take at least double that time.

However, he says that, if transgenic breeding is successful within two years, then a process of exhaustive evaluation will follow, involving some of the most advanced laboratories in the world.

“We must not only prove its nutritional characteristics,” he says, “we must make sure that nothing else in the plant is changed; that in creating a pathway for production of beta-carotene we have not deprived the plant of other biological pathways.

“We must do all this work as quickly as possible. But we must be extremely careful to ensure that, at the end of the day, we can provide all the information, give all the answers, to satisfy the public about its safety.”

An Inseparable Team

The issue of public concern about biotechnology often weighs on the minds of Dr. Datta and his wife, Dr. Karabi Datta. Both are plant tissue culture specialists. As a married couple, they have been together since their university days. Their careers have taken them around the world and, over the past 25 years, they have come to work together as a unique and inseparable team.

Their workplaces are IRRI's plant breeding laboratories at Los Baños in the Philippines,

where tiny shards of green struggle from minuscule specks of tissue in the sterility of crowded incubators.

Attended by research assistants, the tiny plants emerge from a complex process that, itself, still holds the allure of experimentation. But, as they grow beyond their glass flasks, their mystique fades and they appear like any other plot of vigorous young plants.

Swapan and Karabi Datta reject the notion that their work with vitamin A rice represents “the good side” of biotechnology, and that it will restore the technology to political acceptability.

“It is a ‘feel-good’ research project because rice is a cheap food that will easily benefit poor people,” Dr. Swapan Datta says. “It is not an answer to the questions of some nongovernment organizations and nontechnical people who are opposed to genetically modified crops.”

Providing those answers to an often hostile public figures prominently in the Dattas' work.

They oversee the plants' growth to maturity in IRRI's space-age transgenic greenhouse, which is attached to the plant breeding laboratories. Within the greenhouse, they must wear head-to-toe coveralls, reminiscent

of people in space, and they must wash thoroughly before coming out.

The greenhouse is a level-four containment, designed to prevent the release of pollen from the transgenic plants into the atmosphere. Nothing escapes without cleaning, not even the air. Surprisingly, it's the same level of security needed elsewhere for research work with the world's deadliest viruses, such as the dreaded Ebola. It's a harsh reminder that the public has a fearful perception of their work. But, according to the Dattas, attitudes are changing as understanding grows.

Both come from the teeming Indian city of Calcutta. There is perhaps no place on Earth in which to better learn the tragedy of Asia's poorest people. For both, the urgent need to provide for the poor is a powerful driving force.

“If we have the capacity to use this technology to benefit the poor or common people of Asia, for use by subsistence farmers, or to supply domestic markets, then it's work we've got to do,” says Dr. Swapan Datta. “And we cannot do this work half-heartedly.

“In considering the entire controversy of transgenic plants,

As scientists, they stand at the cutting edge of the new biotechnology, specializing in plant tissue culture.

there should be no confusion between other crops and rice,” he continues. “Maize, cotton, soybeans, and others are matters of industrial development. Rice, on the other hand, is food for the poor. It is an agricultural issue. We must make the best use of all the technology we have, while taking all the precautionary measures, to deliver the best product.”

A Need for Caution

Dr. Datta says their work is buoyed by excitement about the new biotechnology among the national agricultural research systems of many Asian countries. He sees the high international respect for IRRI as a force enabling the Institute to take a leading role in the responsible use of biotechnology, aided by trust and cooperation from private-sector interests.

However, he acknowledges the need for caution.

“This technology has developed faster than the public perception of it,” he says. “We must be able to answer the question, How do you know it’s safe?”

“We all have questions and, in fact, I like questions. They should never be avoided. So we must find a way to provide all the answers. I, for one, will continue my science, and I’ll try to find answers to all the questions in a scientific way.”

Dr. Datta believes that thorough testing of transgenic plants is essential, and even suggests the establishment of a quality control laboratory at IRRI, to help prove that the Institute is creating products without risk.

Overall, he hopes a good public understanding of biotechnology will develop within five years. “We can’t afford to wait as long as ten years,” he adds.

Meanwhile, Swapan and Karabi Datta are pressing ahead, within the airtight confines of IRRI’s transgenic greenhouse, with a range of genetically engineered rice plants. As well as the “golden” rice, they are growing a new variety with a bacterium gene for combating stem borer, new plants with additional rice genes for resistance to bacterial blight and sheath blight, and new plants with genes from other plant

species and bacteria aimed at creating an iron-rich rice and improving grain filling.

Already, transgenic plants with resistance to stem borer and bacterial blight, developed at IRRI, are being used in breeding programs in China aimed at transferring the resistances to popular local varieties. ■

“This technology has developed faster than the public perception of it.”

The Dattas’ work in biotechnology has taken them to the United States, Germany, and Switzerland. Dr. Swapan Datta was appointed to IRRI’s staff in 1993, Dr. Karabi Datta in 1996.

They have two children, a 20-year-old son, Samantak, who is studying engineering in the United States, and a 17-year-old daughter, Semanti, who attends International School Manila.

New Plant Type

It is difficult to perceive the job of a plant breeder as stressful, or driven by heavy outside pressure. Experimental greenhouses, with their calm and order, are a world apart from the anxiety of feeding humanity in an overpopulated future, and progress toward developing the rice plant of the future is literally as fast as the rice grows.

A deeper root system; dark green, thick, erect leaves; and 200 to 250 grains per panicle.

"This is an immensely complex process. There are no shortcuts."

Ten years have passed since IRRI's principal plant breeder, Dr. Gurdev Khush, began the immense job of creating a new plant type to help feed a 2025 population of eight billion people. Recently, public clamoring for its release to farmers brought an anxious edge to the most painstaking of jobs.

"A misconception has arisen that suggests that the new plant type will be ready tomorrow," Dr. Khush says. "But what we're making is not a machine. If it doesn't work in some way, we can't take it to pieces and repair it. These are biological materials that we're dealing with. It is an immensely complex process."

It all began with a meeting of plant breeders, agronomists, and plant physiologists in 1989. They concluded that existing varieties of rice had reached a probable yield limit and one of the few means of surpassing their per-

formance was to create an altogether new plant.

So Dr. Khush and his team began the task, knowing it had taken them 30 years of breeding to perfect the "modern" high-yielding varieties that were then, and still are, the mainstay of the world's rice production.

They began by designing the new plant's appearance and they chose, like many other builders, to describe their plans as the new plant's "architecture."

Increasing the "biomass," the total mass of the plant, leaves, stems, roots, and grain, was the key, and the plant's "harvest index," the ratio of grain to straw, had to be higher than that of the existing varieties.

The designers set out to create sturdier stems, so the plant would not collapse under a heavy load of grain. They wanted a deeper root system; dark green, thick, erect leaves; and 200 to

250 grains of rice per panicle, rather than the 100 to 120 grains of modern high-yielding varieties.

Importantly, they wanted the new plant to develop only four or five tillers, the separate stems with clusters of leaves that usually produce panicles bearing the grain. Modern high-yielding varieties grow as many as 27 tillers, and only 15 or 16 of them are productive.

They chose raw materials from Indonesia, the so-called “bulu” varieties of tropical japonica rice, and the long process of crossing began.

By 1995, and thousands of crosses later, Dr. Khush’s team had created its new plant type. It looked like the plant they were after, but many things were lacking.

To begin with, the parent plants took up to 180 days to mature. This had to be slashed back to about 110 days, to allow farmers to grow two crops a year.

Then, the new plants failed to deliver the big harvest that was expected. Many of their grains failed to develop. This undesirable trait was traced back to several of the parents. It took three years of breeding effort to overcome the grain-filling problem.

At the same time, the team found that just four or five tillers didn’t provide sufficient biomass to deliver a big harvest. So the breeding program was adjusted to develop plants that produced nine or ten tillers.

As the “fine-tuning” process continued, modern high-yielding parents were introduced to the breeding program to give the new plants essential resistances to pests and diseases.

So far, new plant type lines have been bred with resistance to blast, bacterial blight, brown planthopper, and green leafhopper, and the breeding effort has turned to providing them with resistance to tungro and stem borer.

But there’s another problem: like its japonica parents, the new plant type produces short, plump grains, while rice consumers in tropical Asia prefer long, slender grains. So new parents have been brought into the program to provide the new plant type with long grains, good flavor, and good cooking characteristics.

Released to Some Countries

While development continued last year, the new plant type was released to some countries so they could begin field testing and breeding their own features into it.

In 1999, China even released one new plant type variety for use by farmers. There, consumers prefer short-grained rice, tungro resistance isn’t needed, and a different climate offers growing conditions different from those in tropical Asia.

At IRRI’s experimental fields in the Philippines, breeding of the new plant type for tropical conditions continues at the deliberate pace of the plants themselves. Each set of new crosses takes an entire life cycle to demonstrate its characteristics and, so far, about 3,000 crosses have been made, using about 60 parents.

Dr. Khush says that it’ll take another two to three years before he’s satisfied the new plant type will be ready for the outside world. Then, plant breeders in individual countries will select the lines for local conditions and multiply the seeds for distribution.

“There are no shortcuts,” Dr. Khush says. “The new plant type will be available to farmers in 2005, at the earliest.”

“The new plant type will be available to farmers in 2005, at the earliest.”

New parents have given the new plant type long, slender grains, good flavor, and good cooking characteristics.

Its maximum yield potential will be 12 tons per hectare in the tropics and subtropics, compared with 10 tons per hectare from modern high-yielding rice. He predicts that farmers currently harvesting 5 tons per hectare from irrigated land will be able to lift their yields to about 7 tons per hectare when they grow the new plant type.

Final Career Stroke

Dr. Khush, who heads IRRI's Plant Breeding, Genetics, and Biochemistry Division, regards the new plant type as the final stroke on a career canvas that has won him world recognition and a World Food Prize. At age 64, he has begun thinking about retirement.

He is eager to emphasize that his final project has involved traditional plant breeding methods, and not genetic engineering. But he regrets what he calls "public misjudgment" of biotechnology.

"Our mission is to help the world achieve food security, and we can do things with genetic

The plant breeding laboratory, where the "fine-tuning" process continues.

engineering that we cannot do with traditional plant breeding," he says.

"But the anti-GMO (genetically modified organisms) groups have both resources and an ability to influence the media. We, the scientists, don't have the

time to address these issues, to help correct public perceptions.

"The danger that I see is that we may be prevented from using this technology to increase food production, and the number of malnourished people will continue to swell." ■

Dr. Gurdev Khush, who grew up on a wheat farm in Punjab, India, and who admits that the motivation behind his life's work has been a desire to help Asia's poorest people, feels happy that he has been able to make a difference." But he worries about the future. He points out that delays in testing genetically modified plants in the field have already made work with the new biotechnology very difficult.

This is okay for the European countries. They have plenty of food. They can afford to do without GMOs. But for Asia and the rest of the developing world, banning GMOs does not make sense."

He goes on to outline a grim scenario: "If we fail to provide food security, food prices will rise sharply and people will take to the streets. Food shortages will lead to political instability and, where you have political instability, you cannot have economic development. Unrest in the

developing world will affect the developed world by reducing trade and slashing the incomes of multinational corporations. This will lead to widespread unemployment and instability of stock markets. The developed nations could be flooded with hungry refugees from the developing world."

Has he got plans for his retirement? Dr. Khush says that "several groups" have contacted him to work in an advisory capacity. But, in any case, he seems unlikely to lose step with mainstream science. His wife, Harwant, has a Ph.D. in educational management; his oldest son, Ranjiv, is a molecular biologist; his oldest daughter, Manjeev, is a medical doctor in San Francisco; and his youngest daughter, Kiran, is in her final year of medical studies at Harvard University. A third daughter, Sonia, is an economist in Washington, D.C., with the Save the Children Federation.

An Unexpected Bonus

With the “fine-tuning” program on the new plant type still progressing, field trials at IRRI in the Philippines have revealed an unexpected bonus: the new plant type is a better performer in the tropical wet season than in the dry season.

Wet-season performance may be a “revolutionary factor.”

IRRI crop physiologist Dr. Shaobing Peng (above left with Dr. Gurdev Khush) discovered that the new plant type was a surprising wet-season performer over two years of field trials in which various lines of the new plant type were grown under conditions identical to those of popular, high-yielding indica inbred varieties IR72 and PSBRc52.

Dr. Peng says that the new plant type’s performance may be a revolutionary factor, particularly if dry-season water supplies for irrigation are limited and farmers begin to concentrate their production in the wet season.

He says that the new plant type lines and the IR72 and PSBRc52 check varieties were transplanted at the same stage of development and received the same input of nitrogen fertilizer. In 1998 trials, they received 120 kilograms per hectare of nitrogenous fertilizer in the dry season and 100 kilograms per hectare in the wet season. In both dry- and wet-season trials in 1999, all plants received 120 kilograms per hectare.

In the 1998 dry season, only seven out of 43 new plant type lines produced yields equal to or greater than that of IR72. But in

the wet season of that year, 30 new plant type lines outyielded or equaled IR72, with the best of them producing 7.7 tons per hectare, or 2.7 tons per hectare more than IR72.

In two trials conducted in 1999, the results were even more pronounced. Only four out of 52 new plant type lines outyielded or equaled PSBRc52 in the dry season. But, in the wet season, 49 out of 58 new plant type lines bettered or equaled IR72, with the best of them yielding 6.5 tons per hectare in the wet season alongside IR72’s 4.3 tons per hectare.

Dr. Peng says that the new plant type appears to perform better in the wet season because it does not collapse under the weight of grain and moisture, and its better canopy structure and fewer, heavier panicles rather than many, lighter panicles allow better interception of limited sunlight.

Dr. Shaobing Peng has also been at the head of a scientific investigation that has established the worrying fact that high-yielding inbred rice varieties, released by IRRI over the past 30 years, are no longer capable of producing the high yields of their early years. Details on page 28. ■

At Last, Tropical Hybrids

It has taken more than 20 years. But, in the first months of the new century, Dr. Sant Virmani believes that he has, at last, proven his point: hybrid technology is a viable means of boosting rice yields in the tropics.

He quotes figures to show the increasing area being committed to hybrids in India (150,000 hectares), Vietnam (200,000 hectares), and Bangladesh (30,000 hectares).

**"I'm running out of people
who doubt the technology."**

IRRI's first experimental hybrid using the new plant type as one parent.

Over the past quarter of a century, hybrid rice production in China has grown to cover nearly 16 million hectares, or half the country's total rice-growing area.

Yet it wasn't long ago that Sant Virmani's early research into hybrid rice was dismissed as an impracticable academic exercise. Its critics believed it would fail on simple economic grounds.

Hybrid rice yields about 15 to 20 percent more than the best of the semidwarf inbred varieties upon which the rice crop of tropical Asia depends. But its commercial viability relies totally upon a technically complex process of producing fresh seed for every crop, rather than the conventional system in which farmers simply save seed from their previous harvest.

When Dr. Virmani first began searching for parental lines for hybrid breeding, he was a postdoctoral fellow at IRRI. It was the early 1970s, and popular opinion held that there was no point in developing hybrid technology when there was no expertise for producing the seed, and no money in farmers' pockets to pay for it.

Then, in 1977, Chinese scientists surprised the rice research community by announcing that they'd created commercial hybrid rice varieties for temperate farming, and Dr. Virmani began the research project that would become his life's work.

The hybrid varieties that had achieved rapid success in China were unsuitable for tropical

farming and their grain quality was regarded as poor. So, new parental lines had to be developed for the tropics.

More importantly, Dr. Virmani had to convince agricultural scientists in tropical Asia that the difficult task of seed production was within their capacity, and that the higher yields and financial returns of hybrid crops would justify the higher seed costs to small-scale farmers.

“I always believed the technology would be accepted, but I didn’t know how long it would take,” he says. “At first, I thought it might take five years. Then I added another five years, and another five after that. Finally, I’m running out of people who doubt the technology.”

The key, as it turned out, was the adoption of hybrid technology in the free-market economy of India. Others soon followed the Indian example. In 1999, Vietnam, unimpressed with the grain quality of Chinese hybrid varieties, introduced an IRRI variety, and Bangladesh launched its hybrid rice program with IRRI’s help.

But despite the clear theory that hybrid technology could provide substantially larger harvests, the obstacles to its

adoption by communities of small, poorly educated farmers have been formidable.

A Complex Process

Producing hybrid seed for every crop is a complex process requiring specific genetic technology. It is based on the fact that rice is self-fertilizing; each plant has both male and female elements. So, to cross two genetically different varieties, one of them must be prevented from fertilizing its own seed. In simple terms, the most common method goes like this:

Hybrid breeders first create a rice line that does not produce viable pollen; it is male-sterile. But it can produce seed if pollinated by another line. So, the male-sterile line is multiplied by crossing it with a second line, called the “maintainer.” In most respects, this is genetically similar to the male-sterile line except that it can produce viable pollen. The multiplied male-sterile plants are then grown alongside a third variety, which is genetically different. The third variety produces viable pollen to fertilize the male-sterile plants, creating fertile first-filial-generation hybrid seeds.

Breeders must involve a range of parents, and create a diversity of hybrids. The different combinations are evaluated for yield, disease resistance, insect resistance, and grain quality. Only the best are selected. Their seeds are then produced in bulk to supply farmers.

The first-generation offspring from genetically different parents exploit a phenomenon known as hybrid vigor. They perform better than both their parents. They have a larger total biomass than high-yielding inbred varieties and produce more grains per unit area.

But if farmers save and plant the seeds of a hybrid crop, the resulting plants will not be

uniform; they will show mixed grain types, and they will have lost their yield advantage. So, new hybrid seeds have to be bought for every crop, and the cost is relatively high.

But Dr. Virmani says that, while seed will add about US\$50 per hectare to the cost of farming hybrid rice, the crop will yield as much as 1.5 tons more per hectare and farmers can expect to earn an additional \$135 to \$200 per hectare.

He says that about 15 commercially usable male-sterile parental lines have now been developed at IRRI for tropical hybrid rice farming. These offer genetic diversity, so that if one or another develops susceptibility to diseases or pests, alternatives exist.

China Offers Help

A big development also occurred in 1999. China, with its years of experience in commercial hybrid production, joined the IRRI-sponsored International Hybrid Rice Network, involving national agricultural research systems in India, Bangladesh, Indonesia, the Philippines, Sri Lanka, and Vietnam.

Dr. Sant Virmani:
“I feel a great satisfaction.”

“I always believed the technology would be accepted.”

A plot of IRRI-bred rice hybrids later released to farmers in the Philippines.

“With IRRI’s expertise in tropical hybrid rice breeding and seed production, and China’s expertise in commercial seed production, we’ll work together to do great things,” Dr. Virmani says. “If any one of the countries just beginning hybrid production recognizes an IRRI rice hybrid that suits local conditions, but they don’t know how to organize production of its seed or how to maximize grain yields, then China will be able to step in to assist in commercializing the technology.”

He says that the private sector has also begun investing in the development and commercialization of hybrid rice technology. So much so that the Asia-Pacific Seed Association, representing many seed companies in the region, has formed a “special interest group” on hybrid rice.

“I’m very encouraged by the many private companies, both national and multinational, who want to bring their expertise in seed production, marketing, and distribution to the hybrid rice field,” Dr. Virmani says. “Many of them also want to invest in hybrid rice by committing their own staff to further research.”

He says that IRRI provides parental lines and other materials to both public and private

organizations on the understanding that these materials are not intended for their exclusive use.

Researchers at the Institute have even designed a self-sustaining system for individual farmers who wish to produce their own hybrid seed. Some training is required, as well as a small outlay for seeds of the parental lines.

Clear Path Forward

Dr. Virmani expects that over the next five years the Asia-wide momentum of hybrid rice production will become self-sustaining. But the path forward for his research is clear.

In the near future, he says, IRRI’s new plant type is expected to produce yields as high as those of the current crops of hybrids. At that stage, his hybrid program will begin using the new plant type as a parental line, and the resulting hybrid vigor is expected to provide yields that are a further 10 to 15 percent above those of the new plant type.

“Then,” he says, “we’ll be heading up toward yields of 15 tons per hectare, from the same irrigated fields that are currently producing less than 10 tons per hectare with high-yielding inbred varieties.”

Another hope in the immediate future is to identify parental lines for the development of hybrid rice suited to rainfed lowland ecosystems.

“I’ve had to struggle to take every step along the way,” Dr. Virmani concludes. “But now, I feel a great satisfaction.” ■

Dr. Virmani and his wife Indu have two children, a 29-year-old daughter, Raminder, and a 25-year-old son, Jusmeet. Both live in the United States.

Biotechnology's Cutting Edge

The relatively new scientific field of genomics—deciphering DNA sequences and their biological functions—is widely expected to be the engine that will drive future advances in plant breeding and crop production.

But it seems it can't be considered at IRRI without thinking back to a past commitment.

IRRI was created 40 years ago to improve the well-being of present and future generations of rice farmers and consumers, and to generate and disseminate rice-related knowledge and technology.

"The vital and powerful information flowing from advances in genomics must remain broadly available."

A "deletion mutant" rice plant showing the effects of having specific genes removed.

These days, the interests of rice farmers and consumers lie exposed to possible harm from the private exercise of intellectual property rights. And in genomics—more so than in other fields—patenting and copyright pose a substantial threat of increasing prices and delaying the extension of benefits to the public.

According to one of IRRI's leading scientists in the field, the Institute must not only advance genomics as it relates to rice research but must also promote the rice-growing world's right to have free access to all the resources and tools of the new science.

Dr. Hei Leung, a plant pathologist and geneticist attached to IRRI's Entomology and Plant Pathology Division, is leading a team of scientists who aim, among other things, to create a public platform to ensure that the vital and powerful information flowing from advances in genomics remains broadly available.

And Dr. Leung says that his team will achieve this by taking the scientific initiative and maintaining IRRI's position at the forefront of genomics research.

The project he is leading represents "the next step"

Dr. Hei Leung: "If we delay this work, then too many things could be held in proprietary territory."

beyond the sequencing of the rice genome.

The international sequencing effort is being led by the Japanese Rice Genome Research Program, and involves laboratories in the Republic of Korea, Canada, China, India, Thailand, the United States, and France. Rice has the simplest genome of all the cereal crops. But it still has 12 chromosomes containing 430 million base pairs of DNA. The international project aims to map the structure of the entire genome, accurately identifying all of the genes. Researchers hope to complete the massive task within ten years, at a total cost of US\$200 million.

"The challenge lies beyond the sequencing project," Dr. Leung explains. "That's where functional genomics begins: discovering the functions of all those genes."

Words Without Meaning

"Put it this way," he says. "Having a completely sequenced genome is like having a dictionary with all the necessary words, but without meanings assigned to

those words. We must complete the dictionary by learning the meaning of the words. To continue the analogy: we hope eventually to be able to use these words to compose essays, to develop new rice varieties. A complete dictionary of sequences and functions will give us a new dimension in plant breeding."

Rather than wait for the sequencing project to finish, Dr. Leung's team is taking the information as it becomes available.

To discover the function of the genes, the team is producing large numbers of "deletion mutants," rice plants that have specific genes deleted. By observing the plants and identifying missing characteristics, scientists can assign functions to the missing genes.

Dr. Leung says that the IRRI team is concentrating first on traits of drought tolerance and broad-spectrum disease resistance.

Extraordinary Complexity

"When we're looking at drought tolerance, we're not looking at

the function of just one gene," he explains. "If that were the case, we'd have it done by now. An estimated 2,000 genes are involved in defense mechanisms for disease resistance. We can now examine the entire genome and, by looking at thousands of genes at once, we can trace the extraordinary complexity with which genes interact to create a particular trait. It is essential that we understand this interaction between specific genes, and how this interaction responds to different environments."

So, from the newly sequenced structure of the genome, Dr. Leung's team hopes to assign basic functions to various genes. Then, it will begin a process called "allelic mining," aimed at understanding natural variations in genetic function. Finally, the researchers hope to be able to synthesize a collection of genetic traits that will produce rice plants much better equipped to yield the bountiful harvests of the future.

The project is drawing on the diverse scientific experience and expertise of various national agricultural research systems (NARS).

By observing the plants and identifying missing characteristics, scientists can assign functions to the missing genes.

Dr. Leung believes that IRRI is well positioned to keep this vital aspect of rice research in the public arena.

Delivering the Benefits

“If we delay our effort to promote the public platform upon which this work must be done, then too many things could be

held in proprietary territory,” he says. “To avoid this, we must encourage collaboration so that information and resources can be shared to promote innovation. IRRI and the NARS of the rice-growing nations have a lot of valuable biological resources that can be used to accelerate the delivery of benefits from genomics research.”

The project is off to a good start. The “public platform,” a functional genomics working group, has been formed by the rice research community. Within the group, data, expertise, and genetic resources will be shared.

Dr. Leung’s research team expects to have produced 20,000 deletion mutants of the popular high-yielding rice variety IR64 by the end of 2000. These lines are being propagated, categorized, and made ready for distribution to collaborators. ■

Dr. Hei Leung was born in China, but grew up in Hong Kong. His first interest in rice was sparked by the beauty of rice fields he saw when on trips away from the concrete and steel of Hong Kong to visit his relatives in China.

His university studies were undertaken at McGill University in Canada and at the University of Wisconsin in the United States. He worked as an associate plant pathologist at IRRI from 1986 to 1989. He then became an assistant and associate professor at Washington State University in the United States from 1990 to 1996, and returned for his second appointment at IRRI in 1997.

His wife, Deborah Cook, is the Canadian-born administrator of the International School Los Baños at IRRI. They have two sons, Kailan, age 10, and Jennings, 4.

Bigger Harvests, a Cleaner Planet

Asian farmers grow about 530 million tons of unmilled rice a year.

That may seem to be a bounteous harvest, but, in fact, Asia's rice growers are gathering little more than half of what scientists say their plants are capable of delivering.

The measure by which farmers' harvests fall short of the plants' potential is called the "yield gap." And reining in the yield gap, by bringing modern, scientifically based management practices to the traditional farms of Asia, offers the quickest means of increasing global rice production.

Speed is of the essence. The price of rice must be kept down so that the position of the world's poor and hungry does not deteriorate. By 2025, Asian rice farmers must increase their output to more than 800 million tons a year.

Most of the increase must come from irrigated farms. These already grow up to three rice crops a year, each with a yield potential of about 10 tons per hectare. Yet the actual yield from irrigated farms averages only about 5 tons per hectare, and the rate at which that production is increasing has recently taken a steep dive. There's widespread concern that keeping up the present pace may be expecting more than the soil can give.

IRRI scientists and their national partners believe that intensive irrigated farming is both sustainable and ecologically benign. But farmers are doing it incorrectly and need to adopt modern technologies.

Rice farmers also find themselves immersed in a problem with water. By 2025, as many as 52 countries, with a total of about three billion people, will have trouble finding enough water for their needs.

In this difficult atmosphere, the yield from each crop on Asia's irrigated fields must climb from 5 to more than 8 tons per hectare in the next 25 years if the world's population is to be fed.

IRRI is leading an all-out scientific effort to help farmers coax the highest possible grain yields from their land, their water supply, their climate, and their personal means. Of equal importance, it is also defining how far those farmers can stretch their natural resources without degrading the soil or damaging the environment.

Debunking the Yield Decline

Are yields from Asia's most intensive rice-farming systems on the decline?

This question has huge implications for the future. Finding the answer has been described as the most important agronomy project in the region.

Just a few years ago, researchers and extension workers in various parts of Asia were inclined to say, "Yes, it looks like productivity is declining," and they would quote figures to support their fears.

If we want to achieve anything in these environments, then we've got to manage things differently.

Dr. Achim Dobermann, a leader in the new approach called site-specific nutrient management.

However, after nearly six years of study, a group of IRRI scientists, supported by a 100-strong team of researchers, seems prepared to debunk the proposition. They've grown uncomfortable with the name of their project: "Reversing Trends of Declining Productivity in Intensive Irrigated Rice Systems." For, although they're not yet certain, the evidence suggests that no widespread yield decline is affecting the world's 80 million hectares of intensive irrigated rice land.

But their studies have brought new insights into the nature of intensive rice-farming systems, and a conviction that, for decades, farmers have been managing fertilizer inputs incorrectly.

They say that millions of rice farmers throughout Asia will need to change their management practices and adopt demanding new technologies if their soil is to be saved from degradation. But the changes promise substantial increases in their yields and their incomes.

Too Much Pressure?

According to Dr. Achim Dobermann, a soil nutrient specialist working with IRRI's Soil and Water Sciences Division, the belief that irrigated rice-land yields were declining came to light after the Green Revolution. Many farmers who'd previously grown only one crop of rice per year were growing two and even

three crops a year on the same fields. The pressure on the soil and other resources became many times greater than before.

National agricultural researchers began to fear that such intensive cropping was not sustainable over a long period.

The IRRI project was launched in 1994 under the leadership of Dr. Kenneth Cassman. Dr. Dobermann took over as its coordinator in 1997.

The project began in IRRI's fields at Los Baños in the Philippines. Long-term experiments there had shown an inexplicable decline in productivity. Using a variety of methods to increase the amount of nitrogen available in the soil, the scientific team was able within a year to reverse the decline on IRRI's experimental farm. Thereafter, the project focused on what appeared to be a steadily declining capacity of the soil to supply nutrients to the rice plants.

But was it a widespread problem, or a local issue affecting just a few long-term experiments? And if it was a widespread problem, was the soil quality decreasing under intensive cropping, or was it the result of incorrect soil and crop management?

With the collaboration of national agricultural research systems (NARS) in India, Indonesia, Vietnam, Thailand, and the Philippines, intensive studies began on about 150 farms. The priority was to begin long-term studies to prove or disprove the decline in productivity. Simultaneously, a massive training effort began. Within three years, about 100 scientists from 15 countries learned how to conduct strategic research into nutrient management.

A confusing picture soon emerged: soil nutrient supplies, fertilizer efficiency, and productivity varied dramatically within small localities. Successful farmers existed alongside farms

that were failing. The use of nitrogenous fertilizer was generally inefficient and bore no relation to the amount of nitrogen already existing in the soil, and the use of potassium was unbalanced.

By 1997, the project gained its full force. China joined, and the number of farms under close scrutiny rose to 205. They were typical irrigated rice farms, but covered the entire range of intensive farming conditions. They were between half a hectare and 40 hectares in size, and varied widely in methods, mechanization, and farming practices.

The aims of the project were refined. As well as measuring the productivity of all the farms over time, the 100-strong scientific team focused on a new approach to managing fertilizer inputs to intensive rice systems, and on organic matter and microbial processes within the soil. Agronomists, soil scientists, economists, entomologists, and plant pathologists were working together, often for the first time.

A New Approach

Now, after monitoring at least six crops from the 205 farms, the project team has gathered an

enormous amount of data that are being used to develop new approaches to sustainable nutrient management.

"This has given us a new insight into these intensive systems," Dr. Dobermann says. "Previously, there was the belief that these irrigated systems were homogeneous, that they were much the same. Little attention was given to adjusting management procedures to specific locations.

"We've found that, if we want to achieve anything in these environments, then we've got to manage things differently. We've been looking at factors from farm to farm, even from field to field on some farms."

The outcome is a new approach called site-specific nutrient management.

It involves determining when during plant growth a farmer should apply each of the three main chemical nutrients, nitro-

"This has given us a new insight into these intensive systems."

The leaf color chart, helping farmers measure leaf color intensity so they know when to apply nitrogenous fertilizer.

The most intensive farming systems in the world. One of three annual crops in an intensive irrigated rice field.

gen, phosphorus, and potassium, and the amounts that should be applied. Taking into account the needs of the plants and, as a consequence of this, factors such as existing soil fertility and the weather, the nutrients are applied at times to maximize their benefits and prevent negative interaction.

Nitrogen, for instance, is applied more evenly throughout the growth of the crop, rather than in large measures at an early stage. The times for its application are determined by measuring the color of young leaves in the rice crop. Dark green leaves indicate a high chlorophyll content resulting from adequate

nitrogen. But lighter, yellow-green leaves indicate nitrogen deficiency, telling farmers they should apply fertilizer.

Dr. Dobermann says that the new nutrient management system generally requires about the same amount of nitrogen as was used previously by farmers, or slightly less, about the same amount of phosphorus, but more potassium.

Over most of the research sites, the new fertilizer regime has boosted yields by about ten percent. On about a quarter of the 205 farms, the yield increase has been as high as 20 percent.

“We think that this approach works,” Dr. Dobermann says. “And it is much better for the fertility of the soil.”

Previously, there was the belief that these irrigated systems were homogeneous. Little attention was given to adjusting management procedures to specific locations.

Hardest Job of All

The research team now faces the hardest part of all: refining high science into something usable by poorly educated farmers, and getting the new management practices adopted across Asia.

Already a simple leaf color chart has been developed from a Japanese prototype to help farmers measure leaf color intensity so they know when to apply nitrogenous fertilizer.

In addition, the team is developing a “fertilizer calculator” and a pocket guide for nutrient management to help farmers decide not only when to apply the various nutrients but also how much is needed.

All three on-farm tools will be available near the end of 2000.

At the same time, complex computer models now comprising the nutrient decision support system for rice will be made available to researchers and adapted for use in training extension workers.

“Having demonstrated that this works in a single field, we must ask our 205 farmers if we can manage their whole farms on this basis,” Dr. Dobermann says. “I expect most of them will agree because, in some cases, the additional benefits can be as high as US\$100 per hectare.

“Then we will move to other farmers in the same area, and later from the village to the province, and so on.”

Dr. Dobermann emphasizes that the implementation of the new technology will depend on NARS, hopefully with the support of nongovernment organizations and private enterprise. IRRI will remain involved to monitor progress, to train extension workers, and to provide scientific backup.

“By the end of 2003, we should be dealing with maybe 1,000 farmers. We’ll have a complete technology developed, we’ll have a complete curriculum for training, we’ll know what’s involved in the extension effort,

and we’ll have all the tools to help farmers adopt this technology. Five years from now, we should be seeing a measurable influence.”

Despite his optimism, Dr. Dobermann does not dispute the difficulty of the task ahead.

“Management of nutrients and water, caring for the ecosystem, is difficult. We are telling poorly educated farmers that knowledge is now the key to their success. It will be very hard.”

As to whether or not productivity is, or was, declining in irrigated systems, he says that it may take another five years before researchers can finally confirm or deny the trend. ■

“Then we will move to other farmers in the same area, and later from the village to the province, and so on.”

Over the past four years, Dr. Achim Dobermann has been at the forefront of efforts to increase production levels on Asian rice farms.

Just a decade earlier, he was harvesting rice near the Caucasus Mountains as a postgraduate researcher when the communist system of the old Soviet Union collapsed, and his life changed permanently.

Soon after gaining his Doctorate of Philosophy in soil science from the Institute of Tropical Agriculture at the University of Leipzig in (then) East Germany, he met a former director general of IRRI, Dr. Klaus Lampe.

Their meeting began a process in which Achim Dobermann was eventually recruited to IRRI’s scientific staff.

The first three years of his appointment represented a collaborative arrangement between IRRI and the University of Leipzig. He became an affiliate scientist at IRRI in 1995 and a principal staff member in 1996.

Dr. Dobermann and his wife Ilwa have two children, Darja, age 10, and Tim, age 7.

IR8: Environmental Victim

Is the Asian rice-farming environment changing?

In these days of environmental awareness and global climate change, it's perhaps not surprising that IRRI scientists have found evidence to prove that change is taking place, and it's happening a lot faster than most expected.

IR8 is a name almost symbolic of the Green Revolution that transformed Asian agriculture in the late 1960s. It was IRRI's first high-yielding modern rice variety, released in 1966 for cultivation in irrigated tropical lowlands.

"IRRI must continually adjust its plant type to keep pace with changes in the environment."

Yet, if it were planted today in the same fields across South and Southeast Asia, rice production in those areas would fall by as much as 20 percent. And nothing important has happened in the physiology of the plant. Rather, the environment and, particularly, the soil and the water have changed.

This conclusion has been drawn by an IRRI crop physiologist, Dr. Shaobing Peng, after growing IR8 and elite indica inbreds under current environments with four different levels of nitrogenous fertilizer.

He points out that, in the late 1960s and early 1970s, IR8 crops grown in favorable conditions often achieved yields of 9 to 10 tons per hectare. Today, newly released inbred indica rice varieties, grown with the best management practices, also yield in the range of 9 to 10 tons per hectare.

Therefore, Dr. Peng says, the yield potential of the inbred rice varieties has not changed for more than 30 years.

Nothing Wrong with the Seeds

In his present-day trials, the maximum yield produced by IR8 was 7.2 tons per hectare from a plot that received 200 kilograms of nitrogen fertilizer per hectare. Records from the late 1960s show that, in those days, IR8 produced 9.6 tons of grain per hectare from the same land, after receiving just 120 kilograms per hectare of nitrogenous fertilizer.

Next, he took IR8 seeds that had been harvested in 1968 and stored in IRRI's International Rice Genebank. They were multiplied and grown in the same way as in the previous experiment. Their performance was similarly depressed, indicating that IR8's yield decline was not due to any changes in the seeds themselves. Rather, changes in the soil and the flooded water system stood out as a probable cause.

Dr. Peng says that the plants seem unable to fully develop a

percentage of their grain in today's environment.

He says that the problem highlights the need for IRRI to continue what he calls "maintenance breeding," adjusting plant types to keep pace with changes in the environment. In effect, he says, maintenance breeding is simply speeding up the evolution of the rice plant.

However, this will merely hold yields at the 30-year plateau. He points out that 44 indica rice varieties have been released to irrigated lowland farmers since 1967, and these account for about 80 percent of total rice production in South and Southeast Asia. Although these varieties have made important contributions to disease and insect resistance, yield stability, shortening growth durations, and helping farmers maximize their production, they have done nothing to improve yield potential.

Radical Developments

Dr. Peng says that more radical developments are required to progress beyond the yield plateau so that Asian rice farmers can meet the demands of the future. Among these, he lists IRRI's new plant type and the theoretical conversion of the photosynthetic pathway of the rice plant to make it more productive.

Meanwhile, rice researchers have to "fix some small problems," such as closing the gap between farmers' yields and the potential offered by their plants, and breeding new varieties for less-favorable growing conditions. ■

More radical developments
are required.

In 1991, Dr. Shaobing Peng was the first Chinese passport holder to join IRRI's staff. Now age 38, he comes from the central Chinese province of Hubei. Before arriving at IRRI, his studies took him to the University of California at Davis and Texas Tech University, in the United States, as well as a research appointment at the University of Florida.

He met his wife, Jing Tan, while studying at Huazhong Agricultural University in Wuhan. They were married in Texas, where his wife gained a Master's degree in biochemistry. They have two children, daughter Mimi, age 7, and son Jingfei, age 1.

Water: Tomorrow's Crisis

Orlando and Virginia

Bernadino are rice farmers in the Philippines province of Bulacan, just north of the capital, Manila.

Like thousands of rice farmers around the world who benefit from modern irrigation schemes, they once took many things for granted: the fertility of their soil, an abundance of sunshine, plentiful supplies of water, and the income from two crops per year.

"Land may no longer be the
scarcest commodity."

Little did they suspect that they would become the harbingers of a modern-day crisis which may soon threaten the security of the world's vital irrigated rice crop.

1997 was an 'El Nino' year, and the wet season rainfall over much of the Philippines was well below normal. As the 1998 dry season loomed, competition for the meagre reserves of water in and around Manila forced the Government to act. Water from the Angat-Maasim Rivers Irrigation System, which normally nourishes the Bernadinos farm, was diverted to the homes and factories of the sprawling Philippines capital.

About 20,000 small farmers were forced to abandon their dry season crop. Twenty-five thousand hectares of land lay parched and fallow; about 125 tons of precious high-quality rice production was lost. For the farmers it was a crushing blow. Many turned to raising pigs and chickens. Others resorted to borrowing money to support their families.

As an emergency measure the Government provided a small allowance for farmers to work on maintaining the canals and channels of the irrigation system while they lay dry and empty.

The Bernadinos were luckier than most. Their five children were grown and no longer dependant upon the farming income, and Virginia had long been part of a local cottage industry, making shoulder bags and school bags, and that earned them a small income.

But their 4.75 hectares was leasehold and their rent was paid in rice. Although they lost an entire crop, the rent for that season was still 2.3 tons of rice. They negotiated a time-payment arrangement, but it will be some years before they recover.

The year without irrigation water was not lost on the Philippine authorities. Work is under way to enhance the storage capacity of the Angat-Maasim Rivers System in the hope that future shortages can be avoided.

Rice Farmers Vulnerable

The event also focussed the attention of IRRI scientists on the growing worldwide threat to water supplies for agriculture; a threat created by decreased water resource development and the lowering of ground water tables, salinization, pollution, and the demands of exploding city populations and water-hungry industries.

Like the small-scale example of the Angat-Maasim Rivers System, agriculture increasingly needs to compete with industrial and urban water users, and rice production, because of its water-intensive nature, is particularly vulnerable to future shortages.

According to IRRI water-scientist Dr. Bas Bouman, rice farmers face not only an increasing scarcity of surface water, but also lower ground water tables and the threat of having to pay more for the water they use. Therefore, he says, they must learn to be more efficient in their use of water.

His current research is evaluating two alternatives to the traditional belief that rice must be grown in standing water. The first involves reducing the water level from a depth of about five centimeters to just the level of soil saturation during either the entire growing season after transplanting or during selected periods in the growing season. The second alternative goes even further and allows the soil to dry out for a number of days before the field is again flooded.

He says the reduction of water levels lowers the pressure head of the water and limits losses through seepage and percolation into the subsoil. These are the biggest single factors in water loss from farmers' fields in rice cropping.

A database has been established using experimental data from field trials performed by IRRI and other scientists in India and the Philippines since the late sixties.

A parallel IRRI research project also seeks to quantify the water-saving benefits to be achieved through the direct seeding of rice on either wet or dry fields.

"So far, we've found that reducing water levels at various stages inevitably leads to a moderate loss of yield, up to a maximum of 10 percent", Dr. Bouman says. "But if you let the

soil dry out, rather than remain saturated, then the yield losses become substantial."

"However—and this is where it becomes exciting—the amount of rice produced per unit of water increases tremendously!"

Growing Water Scarcity

With the likelihood of growing water shortages, Dr. Bouman suggests that, in the future, rice farmers should calculate their yields in grams of rice per kilogram of water used, rather than in tons per hectare of land.

"Land may no longer be the scarcest commodity. If farmers are forced to save water, or if they must pay for the amount of water they use, then they'll want to measure their efficiency in terms of water productivity. However, we must realize that

land productivity, and hence total production, will go down if the amount of water saved is not used for irrigation elsewhere."

New research will focus on the efficiency of nitrogen use under water-saving irrigation techniques in order to maintain or increase land productivity. Experiments have started in collaboration with Chinese researchers.

As well as looking at the problem on an individual farm basis, Dr. Bouman has begun the complex task of studying the Upper Pampanga Integrated Irrigation System, as an example of similar schemes around the world, in an effort to identify areas where improvements can make the entire system more water-efficient.

"If we take the amount of water actually used (transpired) by the plants, and compare this with the amount that is lost getting the water to the field, plus seepage, percolation, and evaporation in the field, then we commonly get an efficiency level of about 30 percent. That means 70 percent of irrigation water is lost.

An irrigation canal flows through the countryside of northern Thailand.

"But is it really lost?" Dr. Bouman asks. "A large amount of it flows back in to the system and is used again downstream. So, instead of studying these losses, we should analyze water flows on a system level and work out where water is really lost; where it is no longer available downstream. That is where we should concentrate our efforts.

"Do we line the irrigation canals? Do we insist that farmers save water at their individual fields? Do we equip farmers with individual pumps? Eventually we will have to look at entire watersheds and build simulation models to see what can be achieved by various interventions. Only then can we make entire systems more water-efficient." ■

Dr. Bas Bouman completed his agricultural engineering studies at Wageningen, in the Netherlands. His Ph.D. work involved remote sensing, and he regards himself as an agroecologist with an expertise in systems analysis.

He arrived at IRRI, accompanied by his wife Stella, and began his current research in February 1999. He expects to take four or five years to complete his present studies.

A Natural Success Story

Dr. Tom Mew, head of IRRI's Entomology and Plant Pathology Division, calls himself a dreamer.

It's not the common perception of a man who has followed a career of high science, but he's adamant: "If you're not a dreamer, then, as a scientist, you won't be an achiever!"

"The key is to use different varieties with different resistance genes. Never again allow the pathogen to dominate."

Dr. Tom Mew's dreams and his science have provided one of the biggest rice research success stories of 1999.

With a simple management strategy, IRRI scientists coordinated by Dr. Mew, in collaboration with scientists from Yunnan Agricultural University, have controlled a devastating fungal epidemic threatening to wreak havoc in the huge Chinese rice crop.

The disease, blast, causes heavy yield losses in temperate and subtropical rice crops. It is one of the most serious diseases affecting rice production in China.

"They were using huge quantities of fungicide," Dr. Mew says, "sometimes spraying a single crop six or seven times. We didn't know what kind of environmental damage that was causing."

Three years ago, IRRI developed a new project in consultation with the national agricultural research systems (NARS) of China, Thailand, Vietnam, and

the Philippines. It was called "Exploiting Biodiversity for Sustainable Pest Management," and its work began at a time when modern agriculture was being criticized as the cause of frequent epidemics and pest problems because of genetic uniformity, high fertilizer and chemical inputs, and high production through the monoculture of single cultivars across large areas.

The blast problem in China involved all these factors. It quickly became the project's first priority.

Recipe for an Epidemic

The scientists reasoned that, in a massive, single-variety rice crop, such as that grown in the Red River Valley of Yunnan, in southwestern China, a single disease such as blast could easily explode into an epidemic. After the pathogen adapted itself to the physiology of one plant, it was then ready and able to attack the remainder of the crop. If there

was biodiversity in the crop, however, and if the pathogen was surrounded by dissimilar plants, it was unlikely to achieve a population explosion.

“Our challenge was to simulate a situation in which natural resistance to pests or diseases was diversified through a varietal deployment strategy in actual rice farming,” Dr. Mew says. “We focused on interplanting, or growing different varieties of rice in the same field. At the beginning, there was doubt and skepticism.”

But an experiment in 1997 covering a few hectares suggested that interplanting could achieve 92 to 99 percent control of rice blast as well as attain an unexpected double success by boosting farmers’ yields, which increased by half a ton to 1 ton per hectare.

In 1998, 812 hectares were planted with hybrid rice and glutinous rice, four rows of one and one row of the other. The crop was sprayed with fungicide only once. Yields reached 9 tons of hybrid rice and nearly 1 ton of glutinous rice per hectare. Even more impressive was the fact that within the interplanted crop the incidence of blast fell to five percent from a common level of 55 percent, and the yield loss dropped from 28 percent to nothing at all.

Chinese rice researchers examine an interplanted field in Yunnan Province.

Last year, the area grew to 3,342 hectares, and the farmers involved boasted that interplanting was providing them with about US\$150 more income per hectare.

Chinese national television got into the act, producing a full-scale documentary on the interplanting experiment. The authorities in Yunnan Province organized a field day for other provincial agricultural researchers. Then they set up training schemes to pass the technology on to others. The Chinese Ministry of Science and Technology also became very interested.

The Idea Catches On

By the end of 2000, the IRRI-Yunnan research team plans to extend the scheme to cover up to 60,000 hectares.

“Eventually, we’ll see the whole Yunnan Province involved,” Dr. Mew says confidently. “That’s close to one million hectares of rice farming.”

“The key is to use different varieties, with different resistance genes. Never plant the same varieties every season. Rotate them. Never again allow the pathogen to dominate. Achieve an equilibrium.”

Dr. Mew says that the success of the interplanting procedure has gone even farther than defeating the blast problem and increasing farmers’ incomes.

Fungicide has been substantially reduced, and he expects that the effectiveness of natural genetic resistance to blast will now last longer.

Previously, genetic resistance, carefully bred into new varieties, lasted only about three years because the blast pathogen quickly adapted itself to the new plants.

Dr. Tom Mew: “One needs to be a philosopher if you’re to be a good scientist.”

Hitting the Jackpot

Dr. Mew says that rice blast is also a very big problem in northeast Thailand.

“Maybe the same approach will work there,” he says. “If it does, then we’ve really hit the jackpot. But this doesn’t start and end with blast. Our interest now is to see what effect varietal or germplasm diversification of rice cropping has against other pests.

“We may not be able to affect endemic pests, but we may, at least, be able to prevent large outbreaks.”

Dr. Mew is quick to give credit to researchers from NARS who collaborated in the biodiversity project, and particularly to Professors Chen Hairun and Zhu Youyoung of Yunnan Agricultural University.

“It is successful because our partners were committed to it,” he says. “They understood it and made it succeed.”

This is Dr. Tom Mew’s 25th year at IRRI.

“When I first joined IRRI, I ate a lot of rice, but I knew nothing about the plant, or growing it, and I’m still learning,” he says. “But there’s no doubt that these years have been the most productive of my professional career.”

The Malaysian scientist is 60 years old and is “looking forward to a few more years’ work before retirement.”

He is concerned that IRRI must continue to provide world leadership in rice research.

“Science is developing very fast, and it will be difficult for IRRI to maintain its leading

position if we don’t work hard and smart. Rice diseases and pests are shifty enemies. If we’re not one step ahead of the problems of world rice production, then we’re never going to be able to solve them.”

He has a few words of advice for his younger IRRI colleagues: “Younger scientists must get out into the field to understand rice; rice doesn’t grow in offices and laboratories. They must quickly establish a good understanding of the crop where it is grown—in farmers’ fields. They must keep one foot in the field and the other in the halls of science.” ■

“It is successful because our partners were committed to it.”

Dr. Mew (bottom right), his wife Teresita (bottom left), their daughters (top left and right), and young Filipino students helped by the Annabelle I-Pin Mew Foundation.

Dr. Tom Mew is perhaps one of the best-known figures in and around IRRI, and not only for his work. His first wife, a Taiwanese plant pathologist whom he met and married while studying at the University of Minnesota in the United States, died in 1987. She had been a popular leader of the charitable organization Suhay, run by the spouses of IRRI scientists, and was well known to the Filipino people living in the villages around IRRI headquarters.

After her death, Dr. Mew formed the Annabelle I-Pin Mew Foundation in her memory. It assists local, academically gifted children through their high school studies.

With great pride, Dr. Mew says the foundation has now helped 51 young people, most of whom have gone on to the university, many of them on scholarships.

Tom Mew has two grown children from his first marriage, a 27-year-old daughter, Joling, who is a sociology graduate of Cornell University, and a 21-year-old son, Peiling, who is studying computer science at the University of Connecticut.

With his second wife, Teresita, he has two young daughters, Jialing, age 8, and Ayling, age 4.

He looks forward to completing a book on rice diseases, writing, compiling, and editing on behalf of a group of experts. But the book, he says, will reflect his philosophies.

“One needs to be a philosopher if you’re to be a good scientist,” he adds, with a twinkle in his eye.

Banking on the Future

IRRI has been engaged in a race against extinction: collecting the seeds of Asia's myriad varieties of wild and cultivated rice before they're overrun by the commercial crops of modern high-yielding rice, and are lost forever.

Why bother?

The answer can be found in the recent environmental buzzword, biodiversity, and the realization that within those wild seeds could be the genes to create the high-yielding, disease- and pest-resistant rice plants of the future.

If there's any opposite extreme to biodiversity, it must be "monoculture." This describes a situation where huge tracts are planted to one genetically similar crop. Such crops are acutely vulnerable to epidemics of disease or pests.

There's been considerable scientific concern about the narrow genetic base of the world's rice crop. But a fundamental diversity is about to take root. The new plant type has japonica parents, rather than indicas, from which all other semidwarf, high-yielding varieties spring.

The road to an even greater genetic diversity can only be traveled if there is easy access to a comprehensive collection of rice germplasm, from which to create new plants.

These new plants may only develop pest and disease resistances to and tolerances for drought, flooding, salinity, acidity, and a host of other soil stresses if the genes imparting these traits can be found in wild varieties.

The seed collections of IRRI's International Rice Genebank are the priceless legacy of countless generations of traditional rice farmers. Collected along with the seeds is the folklore that often leads scientists to discover genetic traits of particular value in improving rice crops.

Maintaining the seed collections of the International Rice Genebank is one of IRRI's most solemn commitments. It's something the Institute does for all of humanity, and the care taken is made more poignant by the knowledge that, for many of the seeds, the genebank is the last line of defense between the rice fields of Asia and extinction.

Poor Farmers: A Need to Think Again

After having spent several years talking to subsistence farmers in the Philippines, an IRRI anthropologist has formed clear ideas about what should be done to improve their well-being and provide them with a viable future.

"Very simple things, with very small amounts of input, can make a huge difference."

Dr. Steve Morin: Talking to the farmers.

The conclusions of Dr. Steve Morin, who works in IRRI's Social Sciences Division, represent a challenge to entrenched attitudes and traditional rice research practices.

Dr. Morin believes his findings apply equally to poor rice farmers in other Asian countries. He says that these are people who have been marginalized by the concentration of scarce resources, including rice research, on a disproportionately small group of intensive, irrigated farmers.

And, while admitting that his recommendations would best be made in an ideal world of abundant funding, he believes IRRI should be making a greater effort to work directly with farmers and extension personnel to pass on to farmers the many advances in rice-farming technology. He echoes the experience of other social scientists when he says there's "a huge disconnection" between the work of research institutes and what the farmers are actually able to try and evaluate for themselves.

Worse still, he says, the knowledge and experience of farmers are being largely overlooked by rice researchers.

Poor Understanding?

"When you don't do extension work—like IRRI—you have this problem of communication: you leave it to others. Research tends to be based on our understanding of what farmers want or need, and this may not be very good."

Dr. Morin argues for greater contact between scientists and farmers, so that farmers can help define research questions.

"The task of scientific extension is too big for IRRI. But that doesn't mean we shouldn't talk to farmers in their fields about research, to make sure they're taking part in a broad and practical effort to improve their lives."

For instance, he says that farmers who wish to grow traditional varieties of rice should be helped to do so. But existing extension services tend to regard them as backward people who need to be dragged into the modern system.

Traditional Varieties

"There's an old truism that traditional rice varieties taste best," Dr. Morin says. "In fact, the cuisine and a lot of cultural

traditions have grown up with these rice varieties. Yet we don't do much research on them. We don't know what the traditional varieties could do if we really applied ourselves to them. And there's the hint that, under correct conditions, the traditional varieties could yield nearly as much as the new high-yielding varieties.

"We should perhaps be studying double-cropping in rainfed lowland systems where the farmers could grow a 'modern' crop followed by a traditional one."

Dr. Morin says that one big hurdle to continued farming of traditional varieties is seed storage by the community or individual farmers.

"The growers of traditional varieties don't have the benefits of a system where they can get good-quality, clean seeds with acceptable viability. The seeds they save themselves may have a shelf-life of only one year and, if we get an El Niño year, or there are typhoons, then their crops are wiped out and they have no more seeds."

He says that the simplest technology could provide plastic drums for seed storage by the community and small cans for individual farmers. These would allow them to store seeds for up to five years, and would cost about US\$25 each.

"We thought fertilizer or seed companies could supply these free of charge. It would be a great promotion—much better than T-shirts—so we're looking for partners who might help us do that."

Dr. Morin says that the concentration of rice research on yield improvement in intensive, irrigated ecosystems has left only meager scope for relieving the plight of remote subsistence farmers.

"We have one group of farmers that has massive support in research and infrastructure, and another group that is marginalized. For these farmers,

very simple things, with very small amounts of input, can make a huge difference."

One way of improving the situation would be to make the knowledge and technology flowing from rice research available to farmers municipally and regionally. In fact, the closer this information is to its end users, the farmers, the better.

The Whole Point

Dr. Morin, an American, joined IRRI in 1997 after completing his Ph.D. studies in applied cultural anthropology among livestock producers in the Indonesian territory of Aceh.

Of his present studies, he says that addressing the needs of resource-poor farmers is not a classical kind of anthropology. Rather, it represents the reasons for him being an anthropologist in the first place.

"If you think about it, the opportunity to learn from farmers, and from technicians and researchers, in all these different places is a great gift. This interaction helps us at least

"The knowledge and experience of farmers are being largely overlooked by rice researchers."

as much as it helps them. They're incredibly generous, and I'm grateful to them all. At the end of the day, if our work has helped just one or two people to improve their lives, then it's worth it. This is the whole point of IRRI." ■

Dr. Steve Morin and his wife Lynne, a physical therapist, have two sons, Eli, age 7, and Patrick, age 3, and one daughter, Frankie, age 5.

Empowering Women

What are the implications for world rice agriculture if a significant slice of it is taken over by women?

This question is the basis for a new research project being undertaken by Ms. Thelma Paris, gender specialist in IRRI's Social Sciences Division, in collaboration with the Cuu Long Rice Research Institute in Vietnam and Thailand's Khon Kaen University.

Are these women equipped with the proper skills, training, and knowledge?

There's a nagging misconception that women are just the helpers.

Many men are known to be leaving the land, on either a long-term or seasonal basis, to find nonfarm employment in cities, and their wives and children are being left behind to carry on the farm work.

“What are the implications of this feminization of agriculture?” Ms. Paris asks. “There’s a universal perception that men are the heads of the household, and that women are just the helpers. Will they be empowered to make male decisions?”

The researchers are questioning families in eastern India, after having interviewed 120 families in northeastern Thailand, 189 in southern Vietnam, and 162 in the northern Philippines.

“The questions we are asking are: If the management of rice farms is left to women, are these women equipped with the proper skills, training, and knowledge required to sustain rice productivity? Do they have access to credit, animals, labor, and capital to manage the farm? Do they

reinvest remittances from male household members in agriculture, or do they spend the money on education, health, food, and other household needs? What constraints do they face to increasing productivity and sustaining food security and income?”

Ms. Paris says that the first aim of the project is to quantify the level of male migration from farming, and to identify the changing roles of rural women.

“Our main concern is that, if women are to maintain the level of farm productivity as well as care for children and the home, then clearly they’ll be overburdened. What are the implications for nutrition, and child care?”

“We plan to identify means of providing a better life for women farmers, in terms of policy, technology, extension, training, income-generating activities, and support services. Two possibilities are the establishment of day-care centers and micro credit for women.” ■

A Race Against Time

The final stages of a worldwide race against time were played out last year in the lowland rice fields of Lao PDR.

And the final scenes of the race were no different from those repeated thousands of times across 23 countries in Asia, Africa, and Latin America.

Rice seed collection in a farmer family's field—a scene that has occurred thousands of times over the last five years across three continents.

"Lao PDR will be a significant contributor to additional food production for the world."

Bent beneath the sweltering November sun, a farming couple hurried to complete their harvest in the village of Vang Houa, in Vientiane Province. Suddenly, they were hailed by a group of four strangers, who approached with collection bags and notebooks. One of them was Ms. Khamzene Phimmavong (third from left above), an agronomist at the nearby Pakchaeng agricultural station.

She gestured to the freshly cut rice. "We want to collect some seed samples of the rice you're harvesting, and get some information about it."

Another in the group was Ms. Chay Bounphanousay (extreme right above), the coordinator of her country's newly established rice genebank. She explained that, by allowing the collectors to take a small sample, the farmers would be contributing to the successful future of Lao agriculture.

An animated conversation followed, during which the group took 60 healthy panicles, or about 125 grams of seed, from the family's harvest. They were told it was a glutinous rice called Nambak, after the district in Luang Prabang Province where it originated. "I'm not too happy with the crop," the farmer's wife (third from right above) commented. "I won't be growing Nambak next year."

Collection Campaign

The campaign began in 1995. It aimed to collect every possible variety of cultivated rice and every possible wild species before farmers turned en masse to popular high-yielding varieties and their traditional ones were abandoned and lost forever. Their seeds are now stored for the good of humanity, to enrich the breeding programs of rice-growing countries around the world.

Ms. Chay Bounphanousay (left) and Dr. Appa Rao inspect the condition of seed samples in the medium-term storage area of the Lao genebank that was established during the biodiversity project.

In all, nearly 26,000 samples were collected from 23 countries—11 each in Asia and Africa, and one in Latin America. But Lao PDR was the most successful. The effort there accounted for more than half the total number of samples collected across the world.

The importance of Lao PDR was recognized early in the project. Unlike nearby Thailand and Vietnam, little had been done there to gather the country's diversity of rice, although it lay within the primary center of origin of the dominant Asian species *Oryza sativa*. Archaeological evidence suggested that the earliest domesticated rice cultivation, involving glutinous genotypes, began there about 6,000 years ago.

So, with a bountiful diversity of traditional varieties and a need to train Lao extension officers in the art of seed collecting, IRRI decided to send a staff member from its Genetic Resources

Center, Dr. Seepana Appa Rao, to live in the country.

And, according to the director of the Lao National Agricultural Research Center, the appointment was timely. Dr. Hadsadong says that the IRRI scientist arrived just in time to save the country's precious rice varieties, before large-scale adoption of modern varieties began.

As well as criss-crossing the country's 16 provinces, its special zone, and the Vientiane Prefecture with teams of collectors, Dr. Appa Rao made it his business to learn the language, and, in collaboration with his Lao colleagues, he trained 150 extension officers in collecting techniques. Their job of saving rice biodiversity is now over, so they intend to turn, with their new knowledge, to collecting and storing other national crops.

Funding for the project came from the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation, which also met the cost of

providing a small medium-term seed storage facility at the headquarters of the National Agricultural Research Center near Vientiane.

Its capacity has since been bolstered by the addition of freezers, giving it a long-term capability.

Storing the Seeds

In the case of each 125-gram sample collected in the field, 80 grams was stored in aluminum foil containers in the Vientiane medium-term facility, five grams went into a seed file, and 20 grams of seed was planted at an upland evaluation site. The remaining 20 grams was sent to the International Rice Genebank at IRRI, where it was placed in long-term storage as a backup to the Vientiane collection.

Already, the collection is being used to improve commercial production in Lao PDR. In particular, about 300 samples of aromatic glutinous varieties are being evaluated for the possible development of high-quality export rice.

The Lao Minister of Agriculture and Forestry, Dr. Siene Saphangthong, who is also a member of IRRI's Board of Trustees, says that the richness of his country's rice genetic resources should be considered a national heritage developed by Lao farmers.

"Through the collection and storage of these resources, Lao PDR, even though it's a small country, will be a significant contributor to the development of new rice varieties and additional food production not only for ourselves but also for the world."

The leader of the nine-year-old and immensely successful Laos-IRRI Project, Dr. John Schiller, gives credit to Dr. Saphangthong and other agriculture policymakers in the government for understanding the need

for crop biodiversity in the first place. He says that, even during a time when food security was a big issue, they accepted the challenge of preserving their biodiversity without reservation.

But much of the credit for the Lao collection goes to Dr. Appa Rao.

Unfinished Business

Although the collection project finished at the end of 1999, Dr. Appa Rao believes that one aspect of his work is still undone, and he and his colleagues are seeking more funding and more time in the field to finish it.

They want to go back to the Lao farmers to document their indigenous knowledge about the traditional rice varieties. For the most part, his collection teams didn't have time to record this information while they were preoccupied with the task of gathering seeds, and most experts agree that information about the collected samples is just about as important as the samples themselves.

Dr. Appa Rao even plans a book on the traditional rice varieties of Lao PDR, and a big part of that would involve interpreting the colorful folkloric names given to the different varieties.

Examples include *Kay Noy Hom* (small chicken, aromatic), *Khen Sua* (hidden shirtsleeve), *Gnod Nang* (super woman), *Gna Thao* (grandmother), *Leum Phua* (forgot husband), *Namman* (fat—often duck or cow), *Pa Siev* (tiny carp), and *Khao Poum Pa* (rice in fish stomach).

According to Dr. Appa Rao, there's a lot more to the names than meets the eye, and it all must be explained by the farmers.

For instance, *Fat* is a term associated with good taste, *Neglected Fields* means the variety can grow under poor soil

conditions, *Mae May* (widow) produces some unfilled grains, *Mehang* (divorced woman) produces so much grain that it keeps a woman too busy to remember her husband, who left her, and *Watching Dog* is a variety with such poor quality that even the dogs prefer just to look at it and leave it uneaten.

So rich is the anecdotal history of rice in Lao PDR that the book may become a labor of love. "The sun is close to setting and I will be retiring soon," Dr. Appa Rao concludes. "So, for the benefit of science and rice, I want to document this information for the coming generations." ■

Collection of farmers' indigenous knowledge is an important part of the process.

When Dr. Appa Rao accepted his position, he had never dealt with rice, although he was deeply experienced with other crops. He'd spent 19 years as senior germplasm scientist at the International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics in his native Hyderabad, in India. Much of his earlier career had been spent combing Asia and Africa collecting traditional varieties of sorghum, pearl millet, groundnuts, and perennial pigeon peas.

"Specific knowledge of rice came quickly to me as I immersed myself in the crop," he explained. And "immersed" is the correct word. Dr. Appa Rao was also responsible for simultaneous seed collection campaigns in Cambodia, Myanmar, Thailand, Vietnam, and southern China, where training was his major emphasis. But he ended up spending about

90 percent of his time in Lao PDR, and his will to get the job done struck a chord with his Lao teammates. Together they amassed about 13,000 samples from the Lao countryside.

But the job has been tough on Dr. Appa Rao's family life.

"My wife Padmaja is a rice physiologist at the Directorate of Rice Research in Hyderabad," he says. "So, she didn't want to come here to be a housewife when her husband was on the road most of the time anyway."

Their two daughters, Sree Devi and Sree Kala, are both medical doctors, one at home in Hyderabad and the other in Omaha, Nebraska. "With the family away, I don't feel so guilty about working long hours," he says. "Nobody is waiting at home."

The Rice Diversity Bank

A restless search over the past five years for some of the last remaining wild species of rice has covered the most remote and underexplored regions of Asia, from the mountainous slopes of Bhutan to the tropical swards of Lao PDR.

Thousands of samples have poured into the International Rice Genebank at IRRI.

It's the most diverse collection of rice in the world.

The head of the International Rice Genebank, Dr. Michael Jackson, hopes that he will soon be able to claim, “We have succeeded in capturing much of the diversity of rice.”

It's with unusual care that Dr. Jackson bears the burden of maintaining those millions of tiny seeds for the future benefit of mankind. And it's a responsibility acknowledged by IRRI's director general, Dr. Ronald Cantrell, in saying, “If our funds dwindled to nothing at all, this would be the last door we'd close.”

As banks go, it must be one of the most benevolent. “We're one of the few banks where you don't have to make a deposit before you make a withdrawal,” Dr. Jackson jokes. But parallels between the International Rice Genebank and banks of the financial kind are inescapable.

The genebank holds in trust about 107,000 germplasm samples on behalf of more than 100 countries. In the past two years alone, more than 13,200 germplasm samples have been received, or deposited, from more

than 13 countries and, within the bank's drying rooms, screen-houses, and growing fields, most of the new seeds have already been put to work, like coins in a savings bank.

The first priority is growing them and multiplying their seeds. Then they're registered and they become “accessions.”

The aim is to collect about one kilogram of seed from each accession. After drying, cleaning, and testing for viability, about 500 grams of seed is maintained in aluminum foil pouches in the bank's “active” collection. One hundred and twenty grams of it is hermetically sealed into aluminum cans and placed in the frigid minus 20 °C vault of the bank's “base” collection, for virtually eternal safekeeping.

Keeping Them Alive

During 1998 and 1999, more than 10,000 accessions were added to the base collection, boosting the total number in long-term care to about 85,000.

For each one, an assessment is made of how long it might remain alive and, after a time, a sample is woken for viability checking.

“Over the past six or seven years, we’ve done something like half a million germination tests,” Dr. Jackson says. “Part of that is following dormancy-breaking protocols for wild species. They’ll only germinate under specific conditions, and we’ve had to learn the preferred germination conditions for each of about 20 species.”

According to the demand for samples from the much-sought-after active collection, the bank’s seed coffers are topped off by annual production crops grown in the fields of the IRRI experiment station in the Philippines.

“If you’re going to produce high-quality seed, then you must match the variety with the environment,” advises Dr. Jackson. “The bright days and cool nights of January and February in the Philippines give us the best conditions for grain filling, so we produce the best seed.”

A Vital Role

Following the 1992 Convention on Biological Diversity, which recognized the sovereign rights of nations over genetic resources,

Sorting and counting seeds. From left to right, Maridee Pontipetra, Romy Aguilar, and Eva Eloria, of IRRI's Genetic Resources Center.

the genebank’s role as a central germplasm supply for many of the world’s rice breeders and researchers has become a vital one.

“Through the genebank collections, researchers around the world can continue to access the diversity of rice germplasm,” Dr. Jackson says. “We have about 20 countries each with at least 2,000 samples in the International Rice Genebank collections. For most of those countries, the genebank collection is more or less a duplicate of their national collection and, in

that respect, we provide an important security backup for them. But we’re still able to distribute this germplasm freely.”

A 1994 agreement with the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) recognizes the “in trust” status of germplasm collections held by members of the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research, including IRRI.

“We don’t own the germplasm,” Dr. Jackson explains. “We maintain it to certain standards, mandated by the FAO, for the benefit of mankind.”

This consideration, together with a constant wariness of claims for intellectual property rights, determines the rules under which the genebank allows “withdrawals.”

Who Owns It?

“IRRI neither claims ownership of the germplasm, nor will it seek to protect it by way of intellectual property rights,” Dr. Jackson says. “We pass this obligation on to the recipients of germplasm samples by way of a material transfer agreement.

Germination testing. Dr. Michael Jackson with research technician Emer Hernandez.

"We will prevent, as far as we can, any inappropriate use, or misuse, of germplasm coming from the collection. If we believe there's been any kind of breach of an agreement, there's an established procedure, agreed with the FAO, by which we notify the authorities who grant intellectual property protection in the different countries."

Dr. Jackson admits that the policy and political environment in which the genebank handles the exchange of germplasm has changed dramatically over the past ten years. But it's had little effect on the bank's "withdrawals." Over the past two years, nearly 13,000 germplasm samples have been distributed for rice breeding or research in more than 27 countries.

As well as bending with the political environment, the genebank is deeply involved in preparing itself to keep up with advances in biotechnology.

Unlocking the Secrets

Germplasm is, these days, routinely described for the appearance of the plant, its cropping performance, and its disease and pest resistance.

"We're unlocking the secrets and potentials of this collection," Dr. Jackson says. "Genetically, it's the most diverse collection of rice in the world, and we're providing labels, much as you might if we were marketing these varieties."

"When IRRI set about creating the new plant type, for instance, it looked to the genebank to find the parental materials."

The genebank is also looking to the possibility that much of its future collection will also consist of stored DNA clones, and it might be sending out DNA instead of seeds.

"We'll soon reach the stage where specific genes are identified and cloned so that the genebank can build up a collection and offer them, ready for use," Dr. Jackson claims. "Our information system already offers details of traits, and linking this information with that from genetic mapping will open up more avenues for use of germplasm. The implications are enormous."

All the genebank's "transactions" are handled by its information system, IRGCIS (International Rice Genebank Collection Information System). It not only

contains the genebank's database but also manages all seed stocks and exchanges of germplasm, coming in or going out.

The system is expected to be up and running on the Internet by the end of 2000.

Dr. Jackson says that rice researchers will then be able to look for the traits they want and order their germplasm electronically.

Surprisingly, while preparing for the technological leaps of the future, the genebank is still very active at the opposite end of the IRRI spectrum.

It is developing cheap devices made from oil drums for drying and storing seeds in communities in the hope that seed supplies to small farmers may be more secure. ■

"We maintain this germplasm for the benefit of mankind."

Much as rice is now a dominant feature of his life, Dr. Michael Jackson's preoccupation used to be potatoes. He spent eight years working at the International Potato Center (CIP), headquartered in Lima, Peru.

"I spent the first three years wandering the Andes of Peru collecting and studying potatoes," Dr. Jackson says. "Then I became leader of CIP's regional program in Mexico, Central America, and the Caribbean, and I spent a lot of time working on bacterial diseases and breeding potatoes adapted to hot, humid environments."

After ten years of teaching at The University of Birmingham in the United Kingdom, Dr. Jackson joined IRRI in 1991.

His wife, Stephanie, is also a genetic resources specialist. They married in Peru, where Mrs. Jackson also investigated the world's potato crop.

Both of their daughters, Hannah, age 21, and Philippa, 17, are students of psychology. At Macalester College in Minnesota, in the United States, Hannah also studied anthropology. Philippa will begin her studies this year in the United Kingdom.

New Directions: Moving Closer to Farmers

Where do IRRI's responsibilities begin, and where must they end?

These issues have taxed the minds of many administrators and scientists over the Institute's 40 years.

IRRI has always insisted officially that its job ends when its scientists publish their findings. It does not take those findings and explain them to farmers. That job is left to the agricultural research systems of rice-growing countries.

But what happens when there's widespread dissatisfaction with the efficiency of that system, both outside IRRI and within?

The Institute has launched a project that hopes to find a whole range of new partners who can help to pass on fresh technology to farmers, so that, ultimately, IRRI may be able to redefine the point at which its job ends.

Then, what if it becomes obvious that, no matter how IRRI's research may equip farmers for improved production, their future is still in serious doubt because their region's development is unplanned and headed for serious problems? Where should IRRI's job begin?

The Institute bit that particular bullet back in 1996, when it stepped beyond its rice research role and became the coordinating body for a far-ranging attempt to bring agricultural and social planning, future land-use plotting, and natural resource management to Asia.

In just four years, that project has captured the attention of senior bureaucrats in at least five countries and has laid plans affecting the future of millions of people.

In a sense, IRRI has expanded its traditional role, showing the Institute's commitment to its 40-year-old goal: "To improve the well-being of present and future generations of rice farmers and consumers, particularly those with low incomes."

Breaking New Ground

The world needs 50 percent more rice, so that, in another 20 years, about four billion people in Asia will be able to wake up every morning confident of getting enough food for an active, healthy life.

"Some people are not even aware that their many planning targets cannot be met by the resources available."

Set aside, for a moment, any thoughts of new plant types, higher yields, and resistance to pests and diseases. Will there be enough farmers remaining on their land in 2020 to grow 50 percent more rice? Will they be able to earn enough money to entice them into "new technology" farming? Will they be able to grow that much rice without damaging the environment? What area of rice-producing land will be taken from them, for urban or industrial development, before it can contribute to future needs?

Are our hopes realistic? The best answer to most of those questions has, in the past, been to consider them as much tied to fate as to planning.

That was before the establishment of the Systems Research Network for Ecoregional Land Use Planning in Tropical Asia—SysNet. It has brought together bureaucrats, politicians, farmers, community leaders, and scientists from a score of disciplines to discuss the management of natural resources and to plan for the future.

The diversity of those involved is such that no existing description fits them all. So

SysNet has given them a new name: stakeholders.

The great success of SysNet is that it has all these stakeholders talking to one another. And, for many of them, that's a new and enriching experience.

After seeing the system in action, high-ranking Malaysian officials want the SysNet methodology applied to their national planning programs. It has also been recommended for adoption by provincial governors and research managers throughout the Philippines.

To Avoid Conflict

The creation of SysNet began in 1996, a few years after IRRI began to sense the huge conflicts that could develop if Asia's swelling population continued to face poverty and hunger simply because of a lack of planning, or because development continued without regard for proper management of natural resources.

With its commitment to the well-being of present and future generations of rice growers and consumers in mind, the Institute stepped into the broad arena of agricultural and social planning,

future land use, and natural resource management.

A team was set up at IRRI to figure out, first of all, how it should be done. The national agricultural research systems (NARS) of India, Malaysia, Vietnam, and the Philippines were soon involved, as was the Wageningen University and Research Centre in the Netherlands. Together they designed the methodology and the “tools” they needed.

Then it was time to test the system. The SysNet team took on four case studies, so it could painstakingly perfect its most vital apparatus: interactive decision support systems for land-use planning, called LUPAS systems. These now consist of complex computer models that take into account the most important biophysical and socioeconomic factors influencing regional development. One such LUPAS system has been created for each region studied, and they’re still being refined for greater interaction with stakeholders, and so planners can see farther into the future.

The Case Studies

The four case studies represent a virtual cross section of Asian rural life and social aspiration. They cover Can Tho Province in Vietnam’s Mekong Delta, Haryana State in northwestern India, the Kedah-Perlis Region of Malaysia, and Ilocos Norte Province of the northern Philippines.

The regions all face rapidly growing and competing demands on land and water. Residential and industrial expansion is constantly eating up farming land while bigger and bigger populations increasingly demand more diversified farm products. There’s also a growing awareness of the need to protect the natural environment and to maintain and, if possible, improve the quality of natural resources such as water and soil. On top of these considerations, all four regions need to lift farmers’ incomes and create greater employment.

According to SysNet’s coordinator, Dr. Reimund Roetter, each study begins with high-level meetings to identify land-use objectives and natural resource

problems. These involve provincial or regional government policymakers and planners and their scientific advisors. Then the study identifies individuals, community leaders, and farmers’ representatives—in fact, anybody who claims a right to co-decide on the use of the land. These make up one group of stakeholders. A second group comprises a multidisciplinary team of scientists, called the SysNet country team. The team is supported by scientists from IRRI and the Wageningen University and Research Centre, and it usually recruits researchers from the NARS of the country concerned.

“Some of the planners realize the need for a total review of what has hitherto been a haphazard process,” Dr. Roetter says. “Resource constraints are known, and competition for scarce resources is acknowledged, but there has still been no analysis of conflicts among economic, social, and environmental goals set for the agricultural sector. There is no established method for planning land and resource use that is based on

SysNet case study 2:
Ilocos Norte
Province, northern
Philippines.

integrated analyses of biophysical and socioeconomic factors; there is no effort to quantify trade-offs between different development goals.

“So we set out to learn together what is technically feasible, given a range of production techniques, given the resource constraints, given the local perceptions of social acceptability. And we consider which problems can be overcome by government policy intervention. In all this, we aim to look ten to 20 years into the future.”

Computer Models

The scientific teams, in regular consultation with local stakeholders, begin creating computer models based on the conditions of the study region. Modeling priorities are identified and relevant data are gathered and added to a rapidly growing bank of information.

Simultaneously, an intensive training effort prepares country teams for the task ahead. Some scientists are trained at SysNet’s IRRI headquarters. Others

undergo local training in computer modeling and data management, while community leaders are lectured on SysNet methodology and take part in interactive working sessions in which their LUPAS system is asked to analyze future scenarios.

Existing crop simulation models are adapted for inclusion into the developing LUPAS system. Satellite pictures and thematic maps are added to give geographical detail. It all takes a few years’ work.

All the time, local stakeholders critically appraise the LUPAS system’s increasingly learned assessment of various land-use and development scenarios.

Then come the “what-if” questions, when scientists and local stakeholders sit down for extended sessions to discuss and elaborate upon the LUPAS system’s responses to questions concerning the future. The system may be asked, for instance, to forecast changes in agricultural production and associated land and resource use if new crops are introduced, if new technologies are adopted to increase production, or if new markets are found.

SysNet case study 3: Haryana State in
northwestern India.

“We have some really intensive sessions,” Dr. Roetter says. “Many of the workshops sit until after midnight, and begin again over breakfast. It is the first time many of the stakeholders have discussed various land-use conflicts, and considered feasible options or compromises. It’s a real eye-opener to some people, who are not even aware that conflicts exist in official development goals, or that the many planning targets for their region cannot be met by the resources available.

“We have agronomists, entomologists, soil scientists, hydrologists, economists, planners, GIS (geographic information systems) specialists, and programmers, and we’re encouraging them to work according to interdisciplinary principles on multidisciplinary teams. I think it has given many people tremendous new insights.”

A Plea for Help

It will be some years yet before SysNet’s impact on resource management in its four study regions becomes tangible. Feasible options need to be translated into policy measures and formal development plans need to be implemented.

But an external review of SysNet after its first three years described it as a project that had made significant contributions to the development of methods for land-use planning and analysis in Asia. It also made a plea for funding to extend the project, saying that discontinuation of support could substantially limit the returns to investments made so far, and could also adversely affect the credibility of agencies implementing SysNet’s recommendations.

Already, SysNet has been invited into two new territories. Work has begun to bring stakeholders together in the Korat Basin, of northeastern Thailand, and in the Red River

SysNet case study 4: Oil palms, an important crop in the Kedah-Perlis Region of Malaysia.

Valley region of northern Vietnam. And the more regions it works in, the more efficient it becomes.

“We’re learning from each site, with different biophysical and socioeconomic settings and resource management problems,” Dr. Roetter says. “In the future, we’ll be able to build on existing computer system components and refine our decision support system for new regions.”

Side Effects

The broad success of the SysNet methodology has also brought beneficial side effects. Within some of the case study countries, the SysNet experience of working together has led local scientists to form multidisciplinary systems analysis teams to tackle other projects.

“There’s also been a gradual but distinct shift in the approach to research,” Dr. Roetter says. “Scientists with SysNet experience have become more flexible. They’re changing from supply-driven to demand-driven research. They’re more willing to ask, and better able to respond to, what end-users want, and this is an enormous change.” ■

Dr. Reimund Roetter, who is a senior research officer for the Department of Soil and Land Use at the Wageningen University and Research Centre in the Netherlands, was seconded to IRRRI in 1996. A specialist in the analysis of land-use systems, his scientific disciplines are agrometeorology, soil science, and crop ecology. He has worked previously in his native Germany, and in Kenya and Turkey, but has found the SysNet experience the most rewarding of his career.

“Personally, it has been very stimulating and exciting for me to work in such a big network with people of so many different cultural backgrounds. First I had to absorb it, then learn and apply the experience, and, finally, give back. You learn a lot, and together you can change a lot.”

Dr. Roetter, whose wife Rosa Maria and sons David, age 8, and Manuel, 6 months, have been with him during his stay at IRRRI headquarters in the Philippines, will return to his home institute in the Netherlands in 2000.

University Without Walls

Of all the evolutionary changes that have shaped IRRI's entry into the 21st century, perhaps the most fundamental involve the work of the Institute's Training Center.

A lecturer addresses IRRI's first rice production course of the new millennium.

"Closer to Asian farmers, and closer to those responsible for agricultural extension."

Over four decades, IRRI's Training Center has taught the latest skills and secrets of successful rice production to thousands of agricultural scientists, technicians, and extension workers. But now its traditional role is under review.

The newly appointed head of the Training Centre, Dr. Paul Marcotte, is eager to create a university without walls, delivering IRRI information to a far wider range of students.

The move promises to shift IRRI closer to Asian farmers, and closer to those responsible for agricultural extension, than it has ever been before. It is, to a large extent, a consequence of the age of the Internet, and a recognition that personal computer use is spreading like wildfire across rural Asia. Distance learning has already become a popular reality.

Recognizing the new training environment, Dr. Marcotte and the head of IRRI's International Programs Management Office, Dr. Mark Bell, are developing a strategic plan to extend IRRI's research information. And the plan hinges on a redefinition of the people and organizations that can deliver information to

farmers. Rather than relying solely upon the extension services of national agricultural research systems (NARS), the Training Center will target both private and public extension services, nongovernment organizations (NGOs), farmers' cooperatives, and even farmers themselves.

It has developed IRRI's first electronic training courses, which can be used either via the Internet or downloaded, translated, and made region-specific for national training purposes. At least one of these is addressed directly to farmers.

Simultaneously, the Institute has launched a major research project aimed at improving future prospects for rice farmers and finding out, at a local level, how the fruits of research and development can be more rapidly and effectively delivered to them.

Bridging the Knowledge Gap

For the past 40 years, IRRI has lived according to the doctrine that agricultural extension is not its job. Rather, it works closely with local researchers, and expects the domestic systems of rice-growing countries to carry

Over the years, thousands of people have learned about rice production, from planting to postharvest, in the Training Center's 2-week course.

the rewards of rice research to millions of scattered farmers speaking hundreds of different dialects.

Although the Institute uses its training capacity to maintain the best possible communication between the NARS and their people in the field, there has long been growing awareness of an ever-widening gap between researchers' discoveries and farmers' practices.

Taking the initiative, several rice-growing countries recently began developing computer networks to deliver information to farmers. And they began urging IRRI to participate.

The man who headed IRRI's Training Center until the end of 1999, Dr. Robert Raab, said that the M.S. Swaminathan Foundation, named after a former director general of IRRI, was supporting the development of information technology networks for farmers in India. A similar effort was under way in Thailand, where the Department of Agriculture was in the process of linking all its research stations and regional offices to a new information network.

He said that both countries had developed community "telecenters" where farmers or

farmers' representatives could seek information on anything from prices to cultural and production practices. They were staffed by technically trained people capable of helping farmers get the information they wanted.

Dr. Raab said that their example was being followed by other rice-growing countries, including the Philippines.

Electronic Courses

As a consequence, IRRI's Training Center has produced three

electronic training or information packages that are available over the Internet or on a CD. Work is also well advanced on updating and digitizing other IRRI courses in preparation for on-line access.

The first is called TropRice. It offers what is described as noninteractive, grass-roots "how-to" information for farmers, including details on plant varieties, planting times, management practices, and even economic assessments. It's on a CD, and is spoken in English. It's designed as a template onto which local researchers can enter new information and advice according to regional conditions.

Eventually, TropRice will also include about 20 specialized training modules. The first two of these already cover the growth stages of the rice plant, and its morphology, or form and structure. Lessons are supported by full-color photographs.

Under a system established by Dr. Raab, local services and organizations using TropRice will accept responsibility for constantly updating the information it offers.

IRRI's first fully interactive training course is aimed at drawing more rice scientists into the computer age. It is called

TropRice can be accessed on the Internet at www.cgiar.org/irri/TropRice.

“Digital Literacy for Rice Scientists.”

Each student undertaking the course is given three “facilitators” with whom to interact. Dr. Raab reasoned that the label “teacher” wasn’t appropriate anymore because the students had access to more information than their tutors. So, in their role of simply guiding students in the proper use of the information, they’re called “facilitators.”

The course also includes a guide to information sources, directing students to recommended Web sites covering a wide variety of scientific disciplines. It is being used in India, and scientists in Thailand are considering introducing it there.

The third course is “English for Agriculture.” It offers 40 lessons, and is interactive in three ways: between students and the course itself, which uses the English language spoken in a variety of accents; between

students and their facilitators; and among the students themselves.

Dr. Raab said that the Training Center concentrated first on English, computers, and statistics because scientists who mastered these three were then ready to move on to specialist areas.

Training Scientists

As well as developing its electronic courses, IRRI’s Training Center supervised degree and postdegree training for 82 scientists during 1999. They came from 19 countries, mainly in the Asian region. Group training courses also continued to cater to a much broader group of scientists from NARS.

Over the years, nearly 6,000 scientists have attended IRRI’s short-term group training schemes, and a total of nearly 10,000 have taken part in the Institute’s training courses, either at IRRI headquarters in the

Philippines or in rice-growing partner countries.

Last year, there were nine courses at IRRI headquarters, which attracted 91 scientists from 18 countries; two regional courses for 26 scientists from nine countries; and 12 collaborative national courses for 185 scientists who also came from nine different countries. ■

The digital literacy training course brings rice scientists into the computer age.

Dr. Robert Raab, former head of IRRI's Training Center, his wife Prasanna, and their sons Lucas, 10, and Joshua, 8.

Delivering New Technology to Farmers

IRRI has, for many years, been confronting a growing dilemma: on the one hand, the Institute insists that extension is not its job; it does not take the results of its research and explain them to farmers. On the other, it has been noticing a growing gap between what researchers know and what farmers are doing.

"The increasing complexity of the information means the job is becoming more difficult. A shift in approach is required."

Dr. Mark Bell (left) with the new head of IRRI's Training Center, Dr. Paul Marcotte.

According to Dr. Mark Bell, who was appointed head of IRRI's International Programs Management Office in January 2000, new technology is not reaching the people who can understand it and effectively use it. This is despite the fact that sufficient technology is available in most situations to improve both the production and the livelihoods of Asian farmers.

So, Dr. Bell is heading a study titled "Partnerships in Communication and Livelihood Enhancement," and his team of researchers is already recommending changes to the traditional arrangement that leaves extension work in the hands of national agricultural research systems (NARS).

"Regrettably, it is well known that most national extension systems are limited in the scope of work they can effectively accomplish," Dr. Bell says. "Knowledge is a major limitation to the productivity and profitability of rice farming in Asia and, because of the increasing complexity of the information that must be passed on, the job is

becoming more difficult. A shift in approach is required."

He believes that the future of extension lies in augmenting the traditional system by drawing on the assistance of NGOs, farmers' associations, and private enterprise. But he stresses a new mood of cooperation, rather than simple reliance on others to perform the task.

"We Have an Obligation"

"A lot of people say that IRRI is simply a research outfit; that it has no place in extension," Dr. Bell says. "I don't buy that. We have the technology, and we have an obligation to pass it on. This doesn't represent a threat to the research effort. It's a matter of getting what we do here applied, by linking up with appropriate partners in the business of development and extension."

Dr. Bell's team has begun work at sites in Thailand, Bangladesh, the Philippines, and India.

"First, we identify what government authorities, NGOs, farmers' cooperatives, community organizations, and private

companies are in a position to collaborate with us,” he explains. “Then, together with these new partners, we go into the field to work out what problems farmers face and what opportunities exist for overcoming them.

“With the right combination of people and skills, you can walk onto a farm and recognize quickly where the potential for improvement exists. The technology is often there, and you therefore have a good opportunity to really improve people’s lives.”

Near Khon Kaen, in northeast Thailand, the IRRI team found itself working with the Thai Department of Agriculture (DOA), with an NGO called the Population and Community Development Association, and with one of the country’s largest banks, the Krung Thai Bank.

The Population and Community Development Association had made its reputation in the field of family planning by playing a significant role in lowering the country’s population growth rate from 3.2 percent in 1970 to 1.2 percent by 1994. While helping the country’s rural poor in this fashion, the association began to consider what else it could do in the fields of agricultural and water resource

development. It offered a perfect partnership for the IRRI team.

On the other hand, the Krung Thai Bank joined the project as a major player as soon as the problem of credit availability became an obvious and critical issue. But the Thai economic collapse intervened and, although the bank remained as an active partner, it was obliged to adopt a reduced role.

Farmers’ Problems

At the outset, it was clear that the farmers of Khon Kaen had three major problems: water stress, weed growth, and nutrient management. So, Dr. Bell’s team called in agricultural engineer Joe Rickman, an IRRI staff member working on the Cambodia-IRRI-Australia Project. He brought in leveling technology to take the dry heights and saturated hollows out of some demonstration rice fields. This, together with improved weed management provided by the DOA, which included the option of a little herbicide, significantly reduced both the water stress and weed growth problems. Nutrient management was a matter of training to apply fertilizers at the correct stages of crop growth.

Then farmers complained that the mechanical threshers they were using were running too fast, and were shattering too much grain. An experienced eye quickly corrected their convictions. Their grain was being allowed to become too dry before threshing, and the problem had nothing to do with the speed of the machine.

“The farmers were very excited,” Dr. Bell recalls. “The fields we leveled were so much better in the following seasons that other farmers lined up to demand that their fields also be leveled. The obvious benefits from a simple range of correct management practices were amazing.”

Who’s Out There?

Dr. Bell says that he expects his project to establish some “rules of thumb” for selecting new partners in the process of developing extension linkages.

“We need to identify who is out there in this gray territory between research, including IRRI and NARS, and the farmers. Then we have to define the characteristics of successful partnerships so we can capture these extension opportunities.” ■

Dr. Mark Bell, who has spent five years at IRRI, was formerly the head of the Institute’s experiment station and interim head of the Agricultural Engineering Division.

He is no stranger to the problems of extension. Before taking his job at IRRI, he was head of crop management research training and head of the experiment station at CIMMYT, the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center, in Mexico.

It was there that he met his wife, Dr. Renee Lafitte, a crop physiologist. Dr. Lafitte is now working at IRRI on improving the drought tolerance of rice.

Drs. Bell and Lafitte have four children, Martin, 9; Leila, 8; and twins Lisa and Miriam, 5.

Program Highlights

Fertilizing the Rainfed Lowlands

A major study in five countries has concluded that improved nutrient management offers the best means of increasing and stabilizing yields of rainfed lowland rice and improving the lot of millions of Asia's poorest farmers and farm families.

Although rainfed lowland ecosystems provide only 18 percent of the world's annual rice crop, they support a large proportion of the rural poor who depend on rice for food security. In these ecosystems, rice is the only crop that can be grown during the monsoon season because of flooding. Production is variable and risky because droughts or floods can occur, sometimes in the same season. Poverty, malnutrition, and underemployment are commonplace.

The study, which began in 1995, involved 78 sites in India, Bangladesh, Thailand, Indonesia, and the Philippines. Agricultural researchers from the five countries played a principal role. The objective was to determine which nutrients were more important for the ecosystems, and how these varied with water regime and soil fertility.

The sites covered a wide range of soil types, topography, and seasonal conditions, including drought and submergence. Popular varieties of rice were grown that were well adapted to local conditions. Each site had six plots, and each plot received a different nutrient treatment: no added fertilizer, farmyard manure, phosphorus and potassium only (PK), nitrogen as well as phosphorus and potassium (NPK), a controlled-release form

of NPK, and an all-nutrient dressing.

Dressings of several fertilizers were often recommended because of infertile soils, and it was found that farmers had a poor understanding of quantities to apply and relationships between the nutrients. They were also reluctant to use fertilizer because of cost and uncertainty in response.

The researchers found that the greatest nutrient response was to nitrogen. NPK increased average yields from 2.25 tons to just over 4 tons per hectare. The effect of adding micronutrients was small, and phosphorus and potassium on their own proved to be of little benefit unless nitrogen was added.

Where water supply was favorable, or where soils had a high clay content, nutrient responses were large. But at drought-affected or waterlogged sites, responses were smaller, especially in regions with severe late drought.

According to IRRI crop physiologist and agronomist Dr. Len Wade, the evidence suggests

that nitrogen dominates the nutrient response, and the size of the response varies with the amount of water available to the crop.

He concludes that substantial yield gains are possible in rainfed systems if appropriate nutrients are applied, and particularly if rice varieties are chosen for their suitability to the local environment. Only in the case of severe late drought on coarse-textured soils is there a small response to additional nutrients.

He says that the project has simplified nutrient recommendations to farmers, because nitrogen has been identified as the dominant factor and variation in demand between soil types has been less than expected.

The next research move is a much more detailed examination of the nutrient supply and crop demand in selected soil types with different water regimes. But, according to Dr. Wade, national agricultural research systems in rice-growing countries can act upon the results already obtained.

A campaign to reduce insecticide use. Dr. K.L. Heong with a poster from the Mekong Delta.

“There is a huge difference between what farmers and extension people know, and what researchers now understand,” he says. “So there is a need for more on-farm work involving researchers, extension personnel, and farmers, to tailor nutrient recommendations to local conditions.”

Dr. Wade says that the ultimate aim of the project is to create a strategic data framework including soil types, water availability, and nutrient responses that will form the basis of a recommendation system for on-farm nutrient management.

Something to Laugh About

Early morning in the verdant jigsaw of rice fields in Vietnam’s Mekong Delta is much the same as it is in any intensive rice-cropping area: farmers and rural workers go about their daily tasks, swathed against the sun, never far from a portable radio.

The ever-present radios have been at the heart of a media campaign that, over the past six years, has had a profound effect on Delta farmers’ use of insecticides. A group of actors has

played out a series of brief comedies, using rustic situations and solid scientific facts to make the audience laugh, and the humorous messages have fixed themselves in the minds of thousands of farmers.

It was an experiment in communication led by IRRI scientists and their Vietnamese counterparts under the banner of the Rice Integrated Pest Management Network. Such was its success that 15 provincial administrations throughout the Delta, and beyond, have now taken over the campaign.

It was based on the premise that farmers’ perceptions, rather than economic rationale, were used in most pest management decisions. It was believed that farmers generally overestimated the seriousness of one particular pest, the rice leaffolder.

The radio drama, supported by leaflets and posters, was first aired in Long An Province in 1994. Research had shown that spraying in the first 40 days after sowing was not necessary, so farmers were told it was a waste of money. They were encouraged to experiment and spray only a

part of their crop to see whether they would lose yield on the part they didn’t spray.

The effects were soon obvious, and by 1997 the campaign had been picked up by 11 other provincial governments and was reaching about 92 percent of the Mekong Delta’s 2.3 million farm households. The results became clear with the analysis in 1999 of intensive surveys.

Insecticide applications had fallen from 3.4 per farmer per season to just one, a decrease of 72 percent. The number of farmers who believed that insecticides would bring higher yields had fallen from 83 percent to 13 percent, and the number who believed that insecticides, as well as killing rice pests, would kill the natural enemies of the pests had risen from 29 percent to 79 percent.

At the same time, the gross paddy output of the Mekong Delta increased from 11 to 14 million tons per year.

One of the leaders of the campaign, IRRI entomologist Dr. Kong Luen Heong, believes that insecticide use can be further reduced by another 50 percent without affecting rice production. He fears that insecticide use will creep up again if the campaigning does not continue.

“The only information the farmers get is advice from chemical companies to use more sprays,” Dr. Heong says. “They think that every dollar they spend on insecticide is going to mean about 13 dollars in their pockets at harvest time. In fact, that far exceeds reality. Even in a worst-case scenario, they might benefit by only four dollars from one dollar spent, and the worst-case scenario is a rare event.

“We should be training people to communicate, to deliver information to the farmers and motivate them to evaluate the new information objectively. In this way, they can improve their knowledge and, at the same time, learn new values.”

An Infinite Memory for Crops

Even in this age of cyberspace, it's hard to grasp the full implications of ICIS, the International Crop Information System.

It's clearly an ambitious project, aiming, as it does, to link and integrate all existing technical information from all disciplines of international crop research into one giant database. But to learn a little about it is to find a new understanding of what computer systems are doing for agricultural research, how much we depend upon them, and what a supreme role they hold in our future.

In the past five years, ICIS has "memorized" the global breeding history of rice and wheat, both of them modern crops whose lineage reaches back over many centuries. Information is now pouring into its memories from Earth's fields of barley, potatoes, soybeans, cowpeas, common beans, and triticale.

The massive information system is being created by researchers for researchers—although they say that agricultural and economic policymakers could also find it useful.

Already, it is delivering lightning responses to plant breeders on questions they previously wouldn't even have asked, because of the time, the distance, and the language difficulties involved in finding answers.

Within ICIS, the various crops have their independent, but integrated, databases. The one dealing with rice is called the International Rice Information System, or IRIS.

Already, IRIS is being used by IRRI's irrigated rice breeding program—the biggest breeding program at the Institute.

The system was first proposed by IRRI's sister institute in Mexico, the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center or, more properly, Centro Internacional de Mejoramiento

Dr. Graham McLaren (center) with members of his IRRI biometrics team. From left to right, Rolando Casumpang, William Eusebio, and Arlet Portugal.

de Maíz y Trigo, CIMMYT.

The idea was put to other international centers grouped under the worldwide funding umbrella of the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research. They, too, saw it as the biggest scientific tool they could provide for their future. A collaborative effort followed, which saw the substantial costs of software development, testing, and training spread around the globe.

The core database of ICIS is called the Genealogy Management System. It identifies germplasm for each crop, in each of their separate databases, in a new and unique fashion: it manages a name recognition system for the known varieties of each crop, and records the chronological breeding history of each.

But the big plus for breeders: it also records data from re-

searchers across all scientific disciplines who are involved in the crop improvement process.

For instance, if a researcher asks for all data recorded about a particular plant line, and asks where seed of that line can be found, ICIS will display all known instances where cultivars of that line have been released for use by farmers anywhere in the world, and it will flag all the susceptible disease reactions they've reported. Already it can also select data from, say, only those trials grown where rainfall is less than 350 mm a year.

According to the man overseeing the creation of the databank related to rice, Dr. Graham McLaren, it's difficult to see where the applications for the vast bank of information will end.

Dr. McLaren, head of IRRI's Biometrics Unit, says that the Institute's rainfed lowland shuttle

Dr. Erik Sacks: clear signs of perenniality in the roots.

breeding program will begin using IRIS this year, to ensure that information is distributed with seeds. Data on hybrid rice breeding and wide hybridization are currently being put into the machinery.

Farther down the line, IRIS will include a module for molecular biologists. It will display molecular data, including molecular markers, alongside phenotypic data and details of physical appearance, for any plant line being grown or researched anywhere in the world. It will also know where to get the seed.

Dr. McLaren has particular praise for a unique feature of the system: researchers using it anywhere in the world will enter their own data as their work progresses, publishing them for everyone else to see and consider. As they do so, they will constantly update the central database.

He says that a compact disc has been released for use as an IRIS database with personal computers. More importantly, work is under way to make the system accessible via the Internet.

As if all that were not enough, IRRI's sister center, CIMMYT, is looking at ways that the infinitely well-informed database can be used in the field of land-use planning and farming systems research. In less than two years, ICIS will offer a crop modeling interface, including data related to fertilizer inputs, water use, and labor requirements.

It takes little imagination to understand that ICIS has been set up for the quantum leap into a scientific future that can already be fairly clearly seen.

For instance, the molecular biology interface for the ICIS database will not restrict itself to single crops. It will be able to search the entire collection of plant crop species, whisking through their entire genealogy with the eye of a molecular geneticist.

"People have stopped talking about different species," Dr. McLaren says. "As long as they find the gene they want, it doesn't really matter where it comes from."

Perennial Rice

Prospects are looking good for the development of a new perennial rice plant for cultivation in upland regions of Asia.

The quest for a plant that would not die after harvesting, but that would go on bearing crops for three or more years, began in 1995. After intensive breeding efforts at IRRI, combining domesticated and undomesticated species from Africa and Asia, field trials have shown that success may be as close as six or eight years away.

Some of the most recent batch of progeny have shown clear signs of perenniality by forming short rhizomes, underground stems that develop both roots and new aboveground shoots. The young plants are also being evaluated for drought resistance.

Rice that doesn't die every year was sought, in the first

place, to help alleviate the disastrous soil erosion and watershed degradation that result from farming traditional low-yielding varieties of upland rice on deforested mountainsides. Erosion reduces the area of arable land in the uplands, and siltation of reservoirs downstream reduces the amount of water available for irrigated rice in the lowlands.

About 100 million people depend on upland rice for their livelihood. They're among the poorest people in Asia, with limited and rudimentary farming options.

A perennial variety would allow them to harvest rice year after year from semipermanent hedgerows. Thus, food production and soil stabilization would go hand in hand.

But, while the new plants are suggesting that success is in sight, much work remains to be done. The new perennial rice will need to yield consistently so that farmers can depend on it to feed their families. It will need to be broadly adaptable to a variety of upland environments, and have enough drought resistance to survive long dry seasons. And the grain it produces must be both palatable and attractive.

Then, special problems are involved with a totally new crop, problems that are not even considered when growing normal rice. When the plants are in the ground for more than three years, how will their roots resist attacks from nematodes (microscopic worms) and, if the plant must recover to grow next year's crop, just how high or how low should farmers cut it when they harvest this year's rice? Work to solve these problems is also under way.

"It's a long-term project," explains project leader Dr. Erik Sacks. "It's like a game of chance. We're looking for rare events—individual plants that combine the best attributes of their wild rice and cultivated rice parents."

Floods Forecast for Delta

A study of Vietnam's Mekong Delta has predicted a difficult future for the region as sea levels rise because of global warming.

The study, undertaken by IRRI and the Vietnamese Sub-Institute for Water Resources Planning, concluded that water levels across most of the flat floodplain would rise almost as much as the sea, adding substantially to the impact of wet-season flooding.

The Delta covers nearly three million hectares and has two and a half million farming households, most of them dedicated to rice production. It is criss-crossed by hundreds of canals and sluices providing irrigation for intensive rice-growing systems that produce up to three crops of rice a year.

It is so flat that the meandering Mekong River falls only one meter in its entire journey across Vietnam on the way to the South China Sea.

The study found that 90 percent of the Delta was likely to be affected by rising sea levels. However, 60 percent of it, about 1,742,000 hectares, was considered "highly vulnerable" with almost unabated rises in local water levels compared with the respective rise in sea levels. What's more, the higher water levels would have the largest effect at the onset and the end of normal wet-season floods by extending the duration of flooding over large areas.

The study used a computer model developed by Vietnamese and Dutch scientists for describing flooding patterns in order to optimize the irrigation system for intensive rice production. The study also used rising sea levels predicted by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change: 20 cm by 2030 and 45 cm by 2070.

It concluded that a sea level rise of 20 cm would increase flood levels across the Mekong Delta by about 12 cm, and a sea

level rise of 45 cm would make the annual floods about 30 cm higher.

But, during the dry season, rising sea levels would be less critical. Water levels would rise in the canal system, but this was unlikely to inundate the land. In fact, higher water levels could reduce costs for pumping irrigation water for dry-season crops.

The study also found that saltwater intrusion would not be as severe as many feared. At present, it said, saltwater intrusion was a major constraint to land use around April, at the peak of the dry season. The salt-affected areas would increase with a rise in sea level, but not to any large degree. A rise of 45 cm would shift salinity gradients only about six kilometers further inland.

One of the authors, IRRI biologist Dr. Reiner Wassman, said that global climate change could have severe consequences for rice production in Asia, and the Mekong Delta had been chosen for the study because of its economic significance.

Tidal wetland rice was cultivated during the wet season in scattered areas along the

coastal plains of Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Myanmar, Thailand, Vietnam, and West Africa. Rising sea levels would not only affect these coastal areas directly, they would also impede the flow of rivers to the coast.

Dr. Wassman said that a previous study had already predicted that about 2.6 million tons of rice a year would be lost in Bangladesh as a result of rising sea levels. While this might represent the most drastic example on a national scale, other Asian countries also had to expect severe consequences.

Dr. Wassmann, who works in IRRI's Soil and Water Sciences Division, added that more than 100 million people lived in coastal areas where about four million hectares of flood-prone rice was grown every year. These were very poor people with generally inadequate nutrition.

He hoped that the report would stimulate further in-depth research on the ecological and economic consequences of rising sea levels and particularly on possible adaptation measures in the Mekong Delta and other coastal areas.

The Mekong Delta, facing problems from global warming.

Diagnosing Tungro

IRRI scientists have developed a diagnostic kit to detect one of the most feared rice viral diseases in Asia: the rice tungro disease complex. The kit, contained in a small cardboard box, has been successfully field-tested and has proven to be reliable in 83 to 89 percent of cases.

Rice tungro disease can devastate thousands of hectares of rice in a single outbreak, such as those in Indonesia in 1995 and in the southern part of the Philippines in 1997. Plants are left yellow, stunted, and totally destroyed, and farmers face ruin. Although major outbreaks are infrequent, there are areas of intensive irrigated rice farming where the disease is endemic and wipes out small pockets of the crop on a regular basis.

One of the obstacles to developing genetic resistance to the tungro viruses has been the expense of traditional laboratory-based testing methods to detect positive infections. Both the equipment and the expertise have been beyond the resources of many national agricultural research organizations.

Dr. Ossmat Azzam and the new rice tungro test kit.

The new test kit contains seven tubes with various solutions, forceps, a pipette, and special membranes upon which sap from a freshly cut rice stem is printed. After the test, the imprinted circles of sap on the membrane turn purple if they're infected and remain clear if they're healthy.

IRRI virologist Dr. Ossmat Azzam says that the kit is simple to use and has been designed for agricultural extension workers and plant breeders. It is particularly useful to breeders because all rice varieties released in the Philippines, Indonesia, Malaysia, and parts of India must have tungro resistance built into the plant.

Dr. Azzam says that, although the prototype kits have worked well, further development is needed. At present, they cost about US\$25 to make. She doubts that production of the kits will be sufficiently profitable to attract private manufacturers, and has recommended that further grants be sought to enable IRRI to make the kits generally available to researchers and crop protection personnel.

Busy Year for INGER

The final year of the old century was a busy one for the worldwide distribution and sharing of rice genetic resources by INGER, the International Network for the Genetic Evaluation of Rice.

The network's aim is to ensure that rice consumers and farmers around the world are able to freely benefit from the evaluation of diverse rice varieties and the development of new cultivars. For 25 years, INGER has coordinated the exchange of thousands of germplasm samples among researchers in 95 countries.

According to INGER's coordinator, Dr. Edwin Javier, 620 breeding lines were organized into five ecosystem trials and four stress trials during 1999.

The seeds originated from the national agricultural research systems of 41 countries, as well as international agricultural research centers like IRRI.

The trials will evaluate the rice varieties for suitability to irrigated, rainfed lowland, upland, or deepwater ecosystems and will determine their tolerance for cold conditions and resistance to bacterial blight, brown and whitebacked planthopper, and gall midge.

As well, 239 nursery sets were distributed to 30 countries for evaluation at 129 test sites. These had been ordered by researchers one year earlier and assembled and dispatched during 1999. Each set consisted of up to 100 varieties chosen for their suitability to specific ecosystems or for their stress tolerance. Three-quarters of the test sites were in Asian countries, and the rest in Africa, Latin America, and Europe.

In addition to the formal trials, INGER organized the distribution of another 358 breeding lines and varieties sought on an ad hoc basis by researchers in 32 countries.

Dr. Javier says that 1999 was notable for the exchange of upland rice germplasm. In collaboration with the Upland Rice Research Consortium, 124 breeding lines from France, Colombia, Brazil, Thailand, India, Côte d'Ivoire, and IRRI were processed and distributed to China, India, Indonesia, and Vietnam for evaluation in field trials.

He says that the value of INGER and its germplasm-sharing system is obvious from feedback from participating countries. After the nursery sets from 1998 were evaluated, 219 entries from ecosystem nurseries and 67 from stress nurseries were used in the varietal improvement programs of 17 countries.

Administration

IRRI underwent a series of leadership and management changes late in 1999 and early in 2000. Some of these were simply the installation of new personnel. Others involved an adjustment to the Institute's management structure.

Dr. Ren Wang

In January 2000, a leading Chinese scientist, Dr. Ren Wang, took up his new position as IRRI's deputy director general for research.

Dr. Wang was earlier vice-president of the Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences (CAAS), where he was responsible for strategic planning, priority setting, and developing major research programs. He also served on an expert advisory panel that drafted China's national guidelines for developing agricultural science and technology over the next 15 years.

Dr. Ren Wang

Dr. William Padolina

In October, the Institute appointed Dr. William G. Padolina to a new position with broad responsibility—deputy director general for partnerships. Previously, he'd been IRRI's director for external relations, with responsibility for resource mobilization, relations with the

Dr. William Padolina

Philippines, and IRRI's research activities with other countries, as well as matters related to intellectual property rights, the training of rice scientists, a large publishing program, and public awareness.

Management Changes

In January 2000, Director General Ronald Cantrell announced several changes to IRRI's organizational structure.

A management group was created for the research divisions, composed of the division heads and head of the International Programs Management Office. Members of this group are now responsible for all personnel and financial matters within their respective divisions, have assumed leadership of research programs, and are serving as members of IRRI's management committee.

As part of the change, the Agronomy, Plant Physiology, and Agroecology Division and the Soil and Water Sciences Division were merged. The new division is headed by agronomist Dr. James Hill. He is also head of the Irrigated Program.

Dr. Gurdev Khush heads the Plant Breeding, Genetics, and Biochemistry Division as well as the Cross-Ecosystems Program; Dr. Tom Mew is head of the Entomology and Plant Pathology Division and the Upland Pro-

gram; and Dr. Mahabub Hossain is leading the Social Sciences Division as well as heading the Rainfed Lowland Program.

Also, in March 2000, Mr. Ian Wallace became director for administration and human resources.

Awards

Dr. Gurdev Khush, IRRI's principal plant breeder and head of its Plant Breeding, Genetics, and Biochemistry Division, was awarded the prestigious US\$100,000 Wolf Prize for Agriculture in January 2000. The Israeli-based Wolf Foundation chose Dr. Khush for his "extraordinary contribution to theoretical research in plant genetics, evolution, and breeding, especially of rice, with regard to food production and alleviation of hunger."

Under Dr. Khush's leadership since the late 1960s, IRRI's plant breeding program has released more than 300 varieties of rice to national agricultural programs in Asia, Africa, and Latin America.

In addition to the Wolf Prize, his native India awarded Dr. Khush the Padma Shri Award for contributions to food security, the Indian Science Congress Association conferred on him the B.P. Pal Memorial Award, and the Chinese Ministry of Agriculture presented him with the prestigious International Agricultural Cooperation Award for his contributions to rice breeding and production programs in China. As well, the Assam Agricultural University in India awarded him an honorary doctorate of science for his outstanding contributions to the welfare of the poorest of the poor.

Dr. Achim Dobermann, a soil nutrient specialist with IRRI's Soil and Water Sciences Division, received the Robert E. Wagner Award from the United States-based Potash and Phosphate Institute. The award recognizes Dr. Dobermann's contributions

to crop yield improvement, and cites his “widely recognized scientific accomplishments in soil fertility and integrated nutrient management.”

Collaborators' Center

In January 2000, IRRI welcomed 38 staff members of ICLARM, the International Center for Living Aquatic Resources Management, as residents of its new Collaborators' Center at headquarters. ICLARM, which is also a CGIAR center, relocated its headquarters from Manila to the Malaysian city of Penang at the beginning of the year. Thirty-five members of its Filipino staff and three internationally recruited staff members have established an outpost office at IRRI headquarters from which to maintain ICLARM's research programs in the Philippines.

They join four staff from the International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT), two staff from the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT), four staff from the International Livestock Research Institute (ILRI), and two staff from the International Service for the Acquisition of Agricultural Biotechnology Applications (ISAA) who were already at IRRI but moved to the new facility.

Information and Training

The past year was busy for new projects by those IRRI departments charged with the task of delivering information to scientists, extension workers, donors, policymakers, mass media representatives, research administrators, IRRI's own staff, and the public.

It was also an extraordinary year for international exhibitions. IRRI staff staged eight international displays, and several in the Philippines, including first-ever appearances at the annual World Bank conference in Washington, D.C., and the American Society of Agronomy meeting in Salt

Lake City, as well as a week-long IRRI-Germany event in Bonn and Frankfurt.

Communication and Publications Services (CPS)

IRRI's four Web sites—The IRRI Home site, Riceweb, Riceworld, and the IRRI Library site—continue to grow in popularity. Nearly 120,000 people visited those sites during 1999. They made more than half a million “hits,” or movements within the sites.

During the year, the Web sites were enhanced by the addition of electronic versions of the 1999 issues of the *International Rice Research Notes*, the *Program Report for 1998*, news about INGER-derived rice varieties, several popular discussion papers, the rolling Medium-Term Plan 2000-2002, IRRI's monthly newsletter *Sandiwa*, and abstracts of recent IRRI conference and workshop proceedings.

More than 200 direct links to useful Web sites were added to the Library Web site.

Credit card sales of IRRI books have continued successfully on the Internet, via the German vendor TRIOPS. Begun experimentally a year earlier, Internet orders have surpassed

200 books. The orders have come from more than 20 countries worldwide. A shopping cart facility will soon be created on the on-line publications catalog to enhance these sales.

Improvements continued to the in-house IRRI intranet, including the addition of weekly features of interest. Several intranet sites, created by IRRI's divisions, centers, units, programs, or research networks, were elevated to the external Internet.

CPS also produced and distributed 25 publications during 1999: six IRRI books, eight installments of the IRRI discussion paper series, six installments of the new technical bulletin series, one installment of the new limited proceedings series, the 40th anniversary 2000 calendar/diary, the director general's report for 1998, the rolling Medium-Term Plan for 2000-2002, and the 1998-99 corporate report, *Hunger or Hope?* At the time of printing, a further 28 books and 10 other publications were in the pipeline.

As well, the familiar periodical *International Rice Research Notes* was given a fresh new format, and a Chinese language version is being considered.

More than 1,100 hours of video in the CPS archives were indexed, a job that will continue with IRRI's still photography collection. The plan is to digitize these images for availability on CD and, eventually, on the Internet.

Public Awareness

A new head of public awareness, Mr. Duncan Macintosh, took up his appointment in May 1999. Soon afterward, a variety of initiatives were launched to focus on donor organizations, the international media, and other key audiences, including IRRI's local community.

These initiatives responded to a greater emphasis by IRRI management on public awareness, including moves to consolidate all of IRRI's many PA-related activities under one distinct unit with its own budget. This PA unit now has a staff of five.

In August, the PA unit launched "The IRRI Hour," a thrice-weekly information and entertainment show on the campus FM radio station at the University of the Philippines Los Baños.

As well, PA arranged 25 radio or television interviews in which IRRI scientists appeared before international audiences. About 60 news releases and more than 100 photographic releases were issued to the world media during the year, covering research developments, new appointments, important visitors, and major conferences.

PA also helped organize 19 events, including special days for nongovernment organizations, the host country, and ambassadors in August.

In January 2000, the PA unit worked together with the CGIAR Secretariat in Washington, D.C., to achieve extensive international media coverage of IRRI's plans to develop rice varieties nutritionally enriched with vitamin A.

Riceworld is an attraction for school-children throughout the year.

IRRI Library

During 1999, 7,445 references were added to the rice bibliography at the IRRI Library, bringing the total to nearly 180,000. As well, 104 dissertations were acquired, mainly from China and the Philippines.

The library's computer equipment was upgraded so that documents can now be scanned and transmitted via e-mail. An audiovisual learning center has also been opened at the library for the benefit of IRRI staff.

Plans have been announced for expanding both the library's rice database and its on-line public access catalog, and for placing 50 years of citations from its Rice Literature Update on CD-ROM.

Visitors, Exhibition, and Conference Services

A fire at the Institute's headquarters in September 1999 extensively damaged the popular Riceworld Museum, depriving IRRI of its principal showpiece for visitors.

Renovations to the fire-, smoke-, and water-damaged ground floor of Chandler Hall began almost immediately, and workmen expect to have a new

and updated Riceworld Museum ready for 40th anniversary visitors in April 2000.

However, the six months without the Riceworld Museum and the Chandler Hall auditorium reduced the number of visitors to IRRI's headquarters. Despite this, more than 38,250 people visited IRRI during 1999, including a royal visitor, 8 state ministers, 39 ambassadors and members of the diplomatic corps, and 11 representatives of various international and donor organizations. To make the restored museum even better than the old one, IRRI has been seeking additional rice-related artifacts and collections related to rice rituals, customs, indigenous knowledge, and traditions.

During the year, the Institute sponsored or co-sponsored and hosted 24 regional and international conferences, workshops, symposia, reviews, and meetings, attended by more than 1,150 participants from 48 countries. All of these were additional to many in-house rice research seminars, workshops, and meetings.

Training Center

IRRI's Training Center provided degree and postdegree training to 130 scientists from 19 countries during 1999. Most of them came from the Asian region.

As well, 51 scholars and fellows completed their programs within 1999.

The Training Center conducted 10 group courses at IRRI for 95 scientists from the national agricultural research systems (NARS) of 18 countries and, in collaboration with NARS in Thailand and the Philippines, conducted two regional courses for 26 scientists from nine countries.

In response to requests from NARS in nine rice-growing countries, the Training Center collaborated to provide 12 local courses for a total of 361 participants, including 185 rice professionals and 150 farmers.

In the past 40 years, IRRI has offered 12,439 training opportunities to NARS professionals from 98 countries. Of these, 2,870 were degree/postdegree scholarships, 5,823 were short-term group training slots, and 3,746 were collaborative in-country training opportunities.

For other aspects of the Training Center's work during 1999, see the feature story "University Without Walls."

The Challenges of Intellectual Property

Of all the issues affecting IRRI's current and future work on behalf of the poor rice farmers of the world, none is as complex, or as potentially disruptive, as intellectual property (IP) rights and their increasing pervasion of scientific exchange and international trade.

At stake, from IRRI's point of view, is the Institute's ability to continue using the most modern science to develop and freely deliver a diverse array of products, including new high-yielding rice varieties, to small rice farmers around the world. Threatening this is the use of IP rights by private interests to acquire ownership of innovations with a view to obtaining profits from their use by others.

IP issues have been the subject of intensive study at IRRI over the past year, including formal reviews of the Institute's IP management practices. The determination of policy has been made more difficult by the fact that different legal regimes or rules apply to different countries and categories of germplasm material. In addition, these different rules and regimes are not necessarily consistent. They may reflect different agreements reached at different times by different international organizations representing different interests and powers.

The Institute's basic policies on IP remain unchanged. They emphasize the free availability of germplasm, information, inventions, and biological material developed at IRRI.

However, the office of the deputy director general for partnerships has now been designated as the focal point for the Institute's IP administration. It has prepared both an IP primer to increase awareness among IRRI staff and a handbook for researchers, aimed at broadly describing laws, documents, and procedures related to IP issues.

IRRI is also developing a standard biological material transfer agreement (MTA) that will accompany all materials

leaving the Institute as "IRRI research products" or "nondesignated germplasm." Recipients will have to sign the MTAs to ensure that any subsequent innovations, based on or derived from IRRI-developed materials and IRRI research, but made and protected by third parties, will automatically remain freely available to IRRI and national agricultural research systems for research and use by rice farmers.

Another similar MTA already applies specifically to the International Rice Genebank's distribution of the so-called "designated" or in-trust germplasm that IRRI holds on behalf of the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization.

IRRI is also developing a standard agreement to govern IP generated by its own staff, guidelines have been developed for implementing partnerships with the private sector, and pro-forma documents have been written for scientists preparing or negotiating collaborative research with IP implications.

IRRI Financial Statement

IRRI's audited financial statements, which provide detailed information about the Institute's finances, are available from the office of the director for finance. The table below provides information on support from IRRI donors in 1999.

Summary of Financial Support to the IRRI Research Agenda, 1999 (US\$)	
Asian Development Bank	823,921
Australia	2,218,559
Belgium	260,383
Brazil	10,000
Canada	
Canadian International Development Agency	704,986
International Development Research Centre	192,363
China	130,000
Denmark	1,140,807
France ^a	185,674
Germany	
Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation	579,092
Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation/German Agency for Technical Cooperation	1,175,213
India	141,936
Indonesia	12,000
International Fund for Agricultural Development	116,894
Iran	114,932
Japan	9,172,567
Republic of Korea	357,487
Mexico	15,000
Netherlands	305,360
Norway	127,110
Peru	80,000
Philippines	109,927
Rockefeller Foundation	1,083,083
Spain	30,000
Sweden	588,028
Switzerland	3,046,524
Thailand	20,000
United Kingdom	1,510,942
United Nations Development Programme	302,514
United States of America	
United States Agency for International Development	3,874,444
United States Department of Agriculture	97,548
World Bank	3,631,339
Others	306,151
Total	32,464,784

^aThe Government of France also provided personnel and other services valued at F 2.14 million.

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About the Cover

Three-year-old Alexandra Isabel Toledo is a Filipino Asian. Fortunately, she has never known hunger. The fact that more and more of Asia's children are like Alex is perhaps one of the greatest achievements of rice research. In her part of the world live 70 percent of the world's poor. Just 30 years ago, the seemingly impossible challenge of matching population growth to increased food production may have condemned Alex, and millions like her, to a life of hunger and want. But, as we now know, rice researchers, in their own low-key way, helped make sure this did not happen. In the process, they showed clearly the rewards of rice research. But enormous challenges remain. Hunger continues to threaten millions in the rice regions of South Asia; many more remain trapped by poverty across the continent. Rice research may be their only hope.

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The International Rice Research Institute was established in 1960 by the Ford and Rockefeller Foundations with the help and approval of the Government of the Philippines. Today IRRI is one of 16 nonprofit international research centers supported by the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR). The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (World Bank), United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), and United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) sponsor the CGIAR. Its membership comprises donor countries, international and regional organizations, and private foundations.

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